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Close Range Orbital Attitude Characterization System

Project Final Report (PFR)

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Project Customers

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Notable Terms Definition

Term	Definition
Client	A physical scale model of an uncooperative and known space debris object.
Characterize	Determine attitude, angular velocity, position, and velocity
Truth Data	Synonymous with measured data, describes the data captured by sensors aboard the client.
Servicer	System that simulates the orbiting (servicing) spacecraft housing the sensor suite and onboard processor

List of Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
TOA ² D ²	Tumbling Object Acquire, Approach, Detumble, and Dock
CROACS	Close Range Orbital Attitude Characterization System
PAB	Professional Advisory Board
FR	Functional Requirements
DR	Design Requirements
V/V or V&V	Verification and Validation
FOV	Field of View
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
CONOPS	Concept of Operations
LIDAR	Light Detection & Ranging OR Laser Imaging, Detection, & Ranging
DOF	Degree of Freedom
FMCW	Frequency-Modulated Continuous Wave
SLM	Spatial Light Modulating
TM	Template Matching
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
LEO	Low Earth Orbit
ICP	Iterative Closest Point
COTS	Consumer off the Shelf
FFR	Fall Final Report
PDD	Preliminary Design Document
CDD	Critical Design Document
PDR	Preliminary Design Review
CDR	Critical Design Review
FFR	Fall Final Report
IDR	Internal Design Review
TRR	Test Readiness Review

1 Project Purpose

Authors: Shawn Stone, Jianai Zhao

As the barrier to entry for space operations decreases, and the commercialization of space increases, the rise in space debris is becoming a growing concern. The Earth-space environment has a growing operational issue due to the increasing amount of space debris, which includes active and inactive satellites, rocket upper stages, and fragmentation debris. Astroscale [1], the company sponsor of this senior design project, is working on end-of-life satellite servicing for inactive client satellites. Servicer satellites, which can be sent to dock, detumble, and deorbit these inactive satellites, require accurate information regarding the client satellite's dynamics. The current ground base satellite tracking systems, which are capable of widespread categorization of debris, still have relatively large margins of positional error, and are ineffective at determining attitude and pointing information for any use in a close range approach environment [2]. Thus, the Close Range Orbital Attitude Characterization System (CROACS) will be responsible for the state determination and state prediction of a client satellite's dynamics to a higher degree of accuracy. This project is especially novel when considering that this is an active area of research with regards to uncooperative satellites in close proximity [3].

2 Objectives and Functional Requirements

Authors: Jianai Zhao, Max Morgan, Tyler Gaston, Shawn Stone

2.1 Project Objectives

For this project, there are three specific objectives that are trying to be accomplished:

1. Remotely sensing attitude, position, angular velocity, and translational velocity of a client satellite

2. Simulate 3D motion of an uncooperative, known satellite for testing
3. Predict future dynamics of a client satellite based on remotely sensed data

2.2 Levels of Success

Level 4		Physical enclosure housing all electronics and sensors	Physical model of client with three axes of rotation		Continuous real time data collection and processing of client model	Software differentiates client from background and models tumble under variable lighting conditions	Software meets accuracy requirements of level 2 and predicts future steady state trajectory
Level 3	Imaging sensor gathers and transmits data to on-board processor, software verifies data is usable		Physical model of client with two axes of rotation	Variable lighting arrangement, various surface materials	Continuous real time data collection, Slower than real time data processing of client model	Software differentiates client from background and models tumble under fixed lighting conditions	
Level 2	Imaging sensor gathers and transmits data to on-board processor		Physical model of client with one axis of rotation	Variable lighting arrangement, fixed surface material	Automatically rotated stop motion imaging data collection of client model	Software processes image data input to differentiate stationary client from background	Software estimates velocities within 1 deg/s and orientation within 10 deg per axis
Level 1	Imaging sensor on test bench that is verified to be gathering data	Electronics, sensors, and other hardware are integrated on simple test bench and organized	Physical model of stationary client	Fixed lighting arrangement, fixed surface material	Manually rotated stop motion imaging data collection of client model	Software received image data input	Software estimates velocities within 2 deg/s and orientation within 20 deg per axis
Project Elements	Sensors and Imaging	Test Bench	Client Model	Testing Environment	Imaging Timescale	Data Processing	Prediction and Accuracy

Figure 1: Levels of Success

In order to meet those objectives listed above, levels of success were created to gauge how well the goals of this project are met. The preceding table contains four levels of success. The first level is threshold, the second level is objective, the third level is intention, and the last level is goal.

2.3 Concept of Operations

Figure 2: CROACS Concept of Operations

The project CONOPS is shown above, and illustrates the narrowed scope of CROACS in relation to Astroscale's larger goal of project TOA²D². CROACS is split into 2 systems, which are the client system and the servicer system. The client system includes a space debris model, which rotates about all 3 axes, and onboard encoders to report truth data. The servicer system includes servicer infrastructure, which is a physical enclosure including all electronics and sensors, on a test stand that has the ability to be rotated and translated during operation. The testing will consist of 5 primary stages. The first stage sees the client model begin to rotate, simulating space debris. The second stage involves the entire servicer system translating on rails to simulate relative motion. The third stage has the servicer LiDAR sensor collect and transmit data to an onboard computer. The fourth stage will have computer software attempting to calculate both current and future attitude states. The last stage occurs offline with the client sensors sending the truth data to the user for accuracy comparison.

2.4 Functional Block Diagram

The functional block diagram has 3 main systems including the servicer system, client system, and power system. The servicer system includes Analog Devices Time-of-Flight (ToF) LiDAR, a rotary encoder to measure translation, and an onboard computer for data processing, attitude calculations, and attitude predictions. The client tumbling system has 2 servos motors and a stepper motor for producing the 3-axis rotation, and they are commanded by a Portenta H7 and Arduino Unos. After the client body begins rotating, the encoders are responsible for collecting the truth data. The power system is powered by wall power, so power is not limited.

Figure 3: Functional Block Diagram

2.5 High-Level Functional Requirements

This project has 5 functional requirements and they are listed as below.

FR	Description
FR1	A sensor suite shall gather data from a scale model of an uncooperative, known space debris object.
FR2	A software algorithm shall be created to analyze the client's relative position, orientation, and angular velocity.
FR3	An on-board computer shall be used for software processing.
FR4	A test bench shall be built to hold the on-board computer and sensor suite.
FR5	A client object shall be created for algorithm testing and demonstration.

Table 1: Functional Requirements

3 Final Design

Authors: Brandon diLorenzo, Jash Bhalavat, Jason Le, Jianai Zhao, Max Morgan, Zack Hubbard, Jake Pirnack, Shawn Stone

3.1 Requirements Flowdown

Listed below are the design requirements, which flow down from the high level functional requirements listed in Table 1 and provide more detail to the goals and objectives of this project. Methods for V/V of each requirement are also listed.

FR 1: A sensor suite shall gather data from a scale model of an uncooperative, known space debris object.

V/V: Demonstration, sensor suite is shown to gather information when properly powered and pointed towards client.

DR 1.1: The sensor suite shall sample data at a rate suitable for a client spinning at a rate of, at most, 10 deg/s.

V/V: Inspection/Test, inspection of the specifications of selected sensor(s) as well as tests to confirm their capability.

DR 1.2: The sensor suite shall have an FOV of at least 15 x 15 degrees.

V/V: Inspection/Test, inspection of the specifications of selected sensor(s) as well as tests to confirm their capability.

DR 1.3: The sensor suite shall be able to gather data from a client at a range of at least 3m.

V/V: Demonstration, simple test confirming data input with client at known distance.

DR 1.4: The sensor suite shall have a range accuracy of at least 10 cm.

V/V: Test/Analysis, first principles analysis based on density of imaging data (point cloud density, picture resolution, etc). Extensive testing to evaluate sensor data

compared to information about the client.

DR 1.5: The sensor suite shall gather data under the harsh lighting conditions representative of satellites in a LEO orbit around Earth.

V/V: Testing, indoor dark room testing using lighting emulating the Sun's rays.

FR 2: A software algorithm shall be created to analyze the client's relative position, orientation, and angular velocity.

V/V: Demonstration, software algorithm displays its calculated values of the client's current relative position, orientation, and angular velocity.

DR 2.1: The software algorithm shall identify the known client from the background.

V/V: Test/Inspection, proportional dimensions of the object identified by the sensor suite be compared to the known dimensions of the debris model to verify the client is well identified from the background.

DR 2.2: The software algorithm shall make predictions of the client's future attitude states.

V/V: Testing, predictions made by the software at a specified time will be compared during post-processing to truth data collected from the client just after this time.

DR 2.2.1: The software algorithm shall have an error of no more than 5% relative to measured data, at a predicted time 1 min in the future.

V/V: Testing, predictions made by the software at a specified time will be compared during post-processing to truth data collected from the client 1 minute after this time.

DR 2.3: The software algorithm shall be accompanied by a software description document to outline its functionality to Astroscale.

V/V: This documentation will be presented to Astroscale periodically throughout the

design process. This will allow Astroscale to make edits and/or comments before the final documentation is complete.

FR 3: An on-board computer shall be used for software processing

V/V: Inspection, external laptop/desktop is not used for software processing.

DR 3.1: The on-board computer shall handle data transfer rates of selected sensor(s).

V/V: Inspection/Test, inspection of the specifications of selected on-board processor as well as tests to confirm its data transfer rate.

DR 3.3: The on-board computer shall have sufficient processing power to be able to compute predictions at least 1 min into the future.

V/V: Analysis/Test, required processing power capacity of on-board computer will be estimated based on selected sensor type and accompanying software algorithm and confirmed through operational testing.

FR 4: A test bench shall be built to hold the on-board computer and sensor suite.

V/V: On-board computer and sensor suite will be placed on test bench to confirm the bench meets its desired design requirements.

DR 4.1: The test bench shall be built to secure the physical electronics in place.

V/V: All hardware necessary for on-board computer and sensor suite will be placed on and secured to bench to ensure appropriate surface area to house hardware. Bench will be moved at desired translation speeds (if deemed necessary) to ensure no hardware moves out of desired alignment or orientation.

DR 4.2: The test bench shall supply the correct power to all hardware and integrate electrical components it is housing.

V/V: Analysis/Test, desired power inputs for selected hardware components of the on-

board computer and sensor suite will be compiled, power analysis will be performed based on their integration with one another, and the external power supplies selected will be tested for achieving desired power inputs.

FR 5: A client object shall be created for algorithm testing and demonstration.

V/V: Inspection, there is a physical object used as a means of algorithm testing and is used in demonstration of the project.

DR 5.1: Sensors from the client shall report measurement data about its position, orientation, and angular velocity back to the on-board computer.

V/V: Demonstration/Testing, client sensors are demonstrated to be sending information back to the on board computer, testing to ensure that the data is relevant (includes position, orientation, and angular velocity).

DR 5.2: The client shall be able to spin at a rate of at least 10 deg/s for on each axis.

V/V: Testing, angular velocity measurement from the client's internal sensors or external measurement device to confirm rotation rate.

DR 5.4: The client's shape shall resemble that of the second or third stage of the selected characteristic rocket body

V/V: Inspection, client's geometry, scaled dimensions, material, and colors will be visually compared to that of the selected rocket stage. Mass distribution, machining of the surfaces, and functionality of components on the model will not be taken into consideration when validating debris model.

3.2 Final Design Overview

3.2.1 Servicer Software

Figure 4: Software Flowchart

The finalized software architecture can be seen in Figure 4. The software begins by reading in the data captured by our LiDAR. This infrared and depth data are then used within Python in order to generate 3D point clouds. These 3D points clouds, and their associated timestamps, are then saved to an archive while also being sent to our main processing stage on MATLAB.

Within MATLAB, there are three main modules for our data to go through: pre-processing, processing, and post-processing. Before reaching the first module, the data undergoes a "data check". This check ensures that the point clouds being sent to our modules are not empty, which is an issue that we saw often when first receiving the data. If the point clouds do not contain any points, then the software will stop and direct the user to the error.

If the acquired point clouds contain points, they are sent to the pre-processing module. This module performs basic data cleaning as well as our vital background differentiation. Unlike in space where this data capture would normally be taken, our software must take steps in order to limit the amount of erroneous points stemming from other objects in the scanning area. Many

items, such as the floor and tabletops, would be captured in the point cloud frame along with our client. To remove this points from the data, geometrical bounding is conducted, which removes all points except those of the client. This bounding is aided by the physical color of the rotating stand, which will be discussed later in the section.

Figure 5: Template Matching

Once the data is clean and bounded to the client, it enters our main processing module that uses Template Matching, whose flowchart can be found in Figure 5. The algorithm begins by computing the centroid of the point cloud, which is the relative position solution of the data. From there, the point cloud enters the matching phase. The acquired point cloud of the client is compared against a template database of the client point cloud at varying orientations. The database is created using a full 3D point cloud of our model, which is then cut is half to better replicate the scanning done by the LiDAR. The point cloud is then oriented at in every possible euler angle combination at a 1 degree step size. In regards to the actual matching, this is done by aligning the centroids of the

acquired and template point clouds at the origin. From there, each point in the two clouds will be evaluated using the mean-squared distance, which serves as our correlation function. All the correlations for the points will be summed and averaged, which is then repeated for every template in the matching set. Once complete with all the templates, the template with the smallest correlation value will be taken as the relative attitude solution.

In order to reduce the lag time from data capture to processed data, two different matching sets are used based on the order of the acquired point cloud. For the first point cloud obtained, the algorithm will only match to the database at a 10 degree step size in order to increase the computational efficiency. If it is not the first point cloud, the previous point cloud's attitude estimate is used as the basis for the next matching set, which deviates 10 degrees from the estimate at a 1 degree step size. This system allows for quicker estimations while maintaining the ability for the data to change with varying speed.

Our post-processing module is where the future prediction of the client's tumble is produced, along with a visual simulation and error analysis. The prediction algorithm reads in the attitude estimates and the given timestamps and performs an euler angle characterization, which takes places in the form of statistical estimation. A linear regression fit is performed to determine the function that best fits the behaviour of each individual Euler angle as a function of time. Once the function is determined, the prediction module then solves each future Euler angle state at all discrete time steps in the user-specified prediction time range. The outputs of the software include error from truth data, a visualization of the client's tumble, and a state vector, both present and future.

3.2.2 Servicer Hardware

The servicer hardware is essentially a computer box with an attached LiDAR sensor. The team narrowed down which electrical components would need to be present, and then the enclosure was dimensionalized to the electrical specifications. The team opted for custom wooden design for

simplicity, cost, and flexibility in the manufacturing process. Figures 6 and 7 below illustrates the CAD and final design of the servicer system respectively.

Figure 6: Servicer CAD Model

Figure 7: Assembled Servicer

3.2.3 Servicer Electronics

Considering the design of the software and the requirement from the customer to move the servicer around, a type of computing system was needed for both the LiDAR and servicer software. The design that was chosen was a normal computer built from the ground up to maximize computing power in areas that would help the software while minimizing another aspect that didn't help the software. The first design point was the CPU. This part will be the brain of the computer and is important to consider as it will determine the speed of the software. Analyzing the first iteration of the servicer software, it was determined that the speed of the algorithm was related to the cores of the CPU. To maximize this aspect, an Intel Core i7-12700KF 3.6 GHz 12-Core Processor was chosen. This CPU is a modern generation CPU, therefore, this was the most processing power the team could have had with the budget. Another design consideration was memory. RAM is another part of the computer that will dictate the processing power of the computer. To maximize the RAM, two Team T-FORCE VULCAN Z 16 GB were part of the final design. This led to the total RAM being 32 GB. Unfortunately because of budget and the compatibility of motherboards (shown in Figure ??) to the chosen CPU, this was the maximum RAM the servicer could have. The other aspects of the computer were accessory parts of the computer to help with thermal control and functionality. These include CPU coolers, fans, power supply, mouse, and keyboard.

Figure 8: MSI PRO Z690-A DDR4 ATX LGA1700 Motherboard

The LiDAR chose was the AD-96TOF1-EBZ LiDAR sensor. This LiDAR is shown in Figure 9 This product was developed and manufactured by Analog Devices. This LiDAR was a time of flight LiDAR. It determines the distance of an object by transmitting a electromagnet wave and receiving the same electromagnet wave back. It then can tell the distance. The LiDAR also had IR capability however that was not used in the design of the overall project. The design choice for the AD-96TOF1-EBZ The AD-96TOF1-EBZ LiDAR sensor was connected to the main computer by the I/O ports on the motherboard. The AD-96TOF1-EBZ LiDAR sensor was composed of two parts. The sensor itself and a dragonboard. They interface with each other by GPIO ports. A USB connection was made from the dragonboard to the servicer computer.

Figure 9: AD-96TOF1-EBZ LiDAR Sensor

For the in-depth analysis of the servicer electronic system, looking at the specific design choice of both the computer and LiDAR. The servicer electronics solve all design requirements for FR 1 and FR 2. Starting with FR 1, the first design requirement, DR 1.1(sample rate should be able to sense 10 deg/s), is through the LiDAR sensor. Therefore 10 frames need to be measured in one second or 10 Hz. To avoid aliasing the minimum sampling that is needed for the LiDAR sensor is 20 Hz. The servicer LiDAR sensor, the AD-96TOF1-EBZ, has a sampling rate of 30 Hz which satisfies the design requirement. The second design requirement from FR1 is DR 1.2(sensor needs to have a 15°x15° FOV). The FOV that the LiDAR that was chosen has a FOV of 90°x69.2°. This is above the FOV from the design requirement in both the vertical and horizontal axis which satisfies the design requirement. The third design requirement from FR1 is DR 1.3(sensor needs to measurement at a range of 3m). The chosen LiDAR sensor has three range modes: Near, Medium, and Far. The near mode can not detect anything after 80cm. This is fine because the medium and far modes can detect at the 3-meter range. They can detect up to 4.5 meters and 6 meters, respectively which satisfy the design requirement. The fourth design requirement that the servicer electronics has to satisfy is DR 1.4 (sensor needs to have an accuracy of at least 10 cm at 1 standard deviation). Looking at the datasheet of the AD-96TOF1-EBZ, the sensor has an error at most 2% at all ranges. Because the client system is designed to be at most 3 meters from the servicer, the error at 3 meters is the explored design space. The error that is expected is a 1.5 cm error at one standard deviation.

This was done by looking at the 2% error to be the maximum error that is seen. A Monte Carlo simulator, where the 2% error is the maximum error, was to determine the standard deviation that will be seen by the AD-96TOF1-EBZ. Figure 10 shows the Monte Carlo with a standard deviation of 1.5 cm. This satisfies the designed requirement.

Figure 10: Monte Carlos of LiDAR sensor

The fifth design requirement from FR1 is DR 1.5(sensor can detect through hard lighting conditions). The sensor that was chosen was a LiDAR sensor. How the LiDAR sensor works is an electromagnetic wave is emitted and then received by the sensor. This does not require lighting like other sensors. Therefore it satisfies the design requirement. Going over the designed requirement for FR3, these are mainly discussing the requirements that are set out for the onboard computer. The first design requirement from FR3 is DR 3.1(the computer can handle the sampling rate of the

sensors). This design requirement is mainly constrained by the i/o ports on the computer. The i/o port that is used on the onboard processor is the USB 3.2 Gen 2x1. This type of USB port can handle speeds up to 2.5 Gbps. 38.1 MBps was determined to be a worst-case scenario based on Ladra's (2019) analysis of the number of points and data rate. For the worst-case scenario, this would be 2 million points per second. Just for 15 minutes of run time, the data coming from the LiDAR sensor should be 34.29 GB. The onboard computer will have a 500 GB SSD which can handle the amount of data coming from all electronic components. With other electronic components not providing as much data rate. This satisfies the design requirement. An overview of these components are shown in Table 2 .

Components	Purpose
Intel Core i7 12 Gen 12 Core	CPU
ATX LGA1700	Motherboard
2x 16GB DDR4-3200 CL16	RAM
500GB M.2-2280 SSD	ROM
Corsair RM 650 W ATX	Power Supply
Fans + CPU cooler	Cooling

Table 2: Servicer On-Board Processor Components

Overall, all the design requirements for the servicer electronic are satisfied. Figure 11 displays the power, communication, interfacing, and how all the components come together.

Figure 11: FBD of Servicer Electronics

3.2.4 Client Hardware

As seen in Figure 12 below, the stepper motor for the client is labelled motor 3, the servo mounted at the end of the L-arm is labelled motor 2, and the servo housed inside the client model is labelled motor 1. Motor 3 has a built-in encoder and uses wired connections to an arduino uno for power and data collection. Attached to the shaft of Motor 3 is the L-arm that holds and moves the rest of the client assembly. Mounted below the end of the L-arm is Motor 2. Motor 2 drives a shaft through the L-arm up to the Motor 1 cluster. The encoder for motor 2 is mounted along the shaft in order to read the data about that axis. Both Motor 2 and its encoder are wired to another arduino uno that is mounted to the side of the L-arm. Finally, the Motor 1 cluster sits atop the shaft driven by motor 2. A 3D printed structure secures Motor 1, its magnetic encoder, a third arduino uno, a 9V battery, and the belt system that translates rotation from the servo to a shaft that runs along the long axis of the client model. This entire system is mounted to a steel U-channel that is mounted

perpendicular to a quarter-inch thick steel base that is reinforced with wood along the bottom.

The client model, the 1/82 scale Saturn V second stage is 1ft long, 6 inches wide, and was 3D printed in two halves so that they could be assembled around the Motor 1 cluster.

Figure 12: Client CAD Model

Figure 13: Assembled Client

3.2.5 Client Electronics

Each motor/servo on the client was controlled by an Arduino Uno Wifi Rev 2. Each motor/servo had an encoder to measure its rotation. Both the servos (motors 1 and 2) were completely wireless as their clusters were powered by 9V batteries that also powered the Arduinos and the encoders. The data rate for the encoder is 2 KB/s. The arduinos received their commands and transmitted their data via Wifi. The stepper motor (motor 3) was also controlled by the Arduino and driven by an HSC86A driver. The stepper was already integrated with an encoder and its values were read by the driver and transmitted to the Arduino. The stepper was powered by a Drok 200570 power supply and the Arduino was powered by a 9V battery. This Arduino was also connected to the Wifi so that all three motors could be controlled simultaneously. The Wifi communications included uplink and downlink commands. The uplink commands were the PWM (Pulse Width Modulation) signals for the servo and command signals for the stepper. The downlink data was encoder data from each corresponding encoder. Initially, phone hotspots were used to connect the arduinos to the wifi. But, that lead to spontaneous termination of the signal and hence, a router has been used from then on. The arduinos are connected to the router's wifi and so is the laptop which acts as the hub for the uplink commands and downlink data.

4 Manufacturing

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4.1 Manufacturing Scope

Because manufacturability was prominent when creating the final design for the CROACS project, manufacturing began as soon as the spring semester started. All of the components needing custom fabrication were designed to be manufactured by the team whether inside the manufacturing shops or off-site. A manufacturing schedule was created before the spring semester began in order

Figure 14: Client Electronics

to get a timeline to follow and allow testing of systems that had been manufactured early while others were still in the fabrication process. The figure below illustrates this schedule.

Figure 15: Manufacturing Schedule

As seen in Figure 15, the timeline was broken down into specific components needing custom manufacturing, and in parallel hardware could be assembled as soon as a component was fabricated. It was anticipated that the fabrication process would take around 3 weeks, with final assembly and integration beginning in the last week of January. This was found to be extremely optimistic and instead the manufacturing process ran until the first week of March. The reason for these delays is discussed in Section 4.6.

4.2 Structural Manufacturing

As can be seen in the final design section, most of the CROACS project hardware involved structural manufacturing. The subsections below are specific to the servicer and client respectively.

4.2.1 Servicer

The servicer system was designed to be fabricated from hardwood, cut and assembled by the team members off-site. A sheet of hardwood was purchased and the enclosure dimensions measured and cut to size. The box shape was achieved by assembling the walls with wood glue and small screws, then cut short and wood pasted over. The entire enclosure was then painted green and black trim added for cosmetics. A shelf was added to elevate the power supply and holes cut in order to mount the fans. The front panel was designed to hinge down, and so cabinet hinges were purchased and mounted with screws to achieve the hinge action. The top is a removable lid made from wood. Lastly the LiDAR sensor was mounted and a corresponding window for it to sense from inside the enclosure was cut. The stand for the enclosure has an aluminum 8020 base, enabling it to slide along the 5ft 8020 track rails. To elevate the enclosure, a 4x4 piece of wood was cut to the desired height and mounted on the 8020 base using purchased angle brackets. Structural support was added with 1x1 pieces of wood epoxied to the base and center stand. A seat swivel is mounted to the top of the center stand using large screws, and a flat piece of wood is then mounted to the top side of the swivel. The enclosure has push pins mounted to the outside of the walls close to the bottom. When the enclosure is mounted to the stand, it sits on the top plate mounted to the swivel, and the push pins are inserted into that plate to prevent the enclosure from sliding on the plate. The figures below illustrate the fabricated and assembled enclosure and stand that make up the servicer system.

Figure 16: Fabricated Servicer System

4.2.2 Client

The client system was designed largely out of fabricated metal and 3D printed components. The Servicer is comprised of the Saturn V second stage rocket booster, 3D printed and painted. This model can separate in the middle in order to access components that enable the roll rotation, housed inside the client. This includes the motor 1 cluster, also 3D printed to hold the Arduino board, encoder, pulleys and belts. A rod is mounted through the cluster and attached to both sides of the model in order to rotate. The connection point in the middle of the model includes a 3D printed slip ring to allow smooth rotation of both sides while mitigating black/blank space seen by the LiDAR sensors. The figures below illustrate the printed model and completed motor 1 cluster.

(a) Saturn V Second Stage

(b) Motor 1 Cluster

Figure 17: Fabricated Space Debris Assembly

In order to create the yawing motion of the model debris, and seen in Figure 17b, the motor 1 cluster is connected to a vertical aluminum rod, the end of which is mounted through an aluminum L-arm and driven by motor 2. The L-arm design was manufactured from a purchased aluminum plate and fabricated using a CNC mill. Bearings are friction fit on the L-arm in the motor 2 input shaft to prevent a fulcrum. A clamp adaptor was purchased and connects the motor 2 rod to the output shaft of motor 2. The other end of the L-arm was milled to the dimension of the output shaft of motor 3 and secured using two small bolts through the top and penetrating through the output shaft keyhole. The fabricated L-arm and motor 2 cluster can be seen below.

Figure 18: Fabricated L-arm Assembly

Lastly the stand to turn the L-arm and lift the entire assembly was constructed. This was U-channel steel and a steel plate welded together at 90 degrees. After welding, a base of wood was constructed from 2x4 peices cut to the lenght of the steel plate. This was planed to ensure a level finish and then secured to the plate with large bolts to prevent bending. Motor three is connected to the U-channel by four bolts and held up by a 3D printed support bracket also bolted to the U-channel. The output shaft of motor three is then connected to the L-arm. The figure below illustrates the base plate, as well as the entire client assembly.

Figure 19: Fully Fabricated Client Assembly

4.3 Electrical Manufacturing

The electrical manufacturing for project CROACS involved using commercial off-the-shelf products, and simply making connections between them using wire and solder. The arduinos are connected to the motor wires and encoders through pin connections. The arduino in the motor 1 cluster is mounted onto the plastic housing. The arduino controlling motor 2 is mounted to the L-arm using a plastic housing and zip-ties. Motor 3 is mounted to a planetary gearbox with bolts, and the wires are connected to a driver with screw-in connections. Every arduino is wired to a 9V battery for power. Inside the servicer is a motherboard computer, suspended from the bottom of the servicer

by an acrylic plate. The LiDAR sensor is mounted to the side of the enclosure using a screw, and connected to the motherboard through USB-c cables. The entire enclosure electronics is powered by wall power.

In the following figure, Figure 20 shows the electronic setup of motor 1. The encoder follows a I2C communication protocol. This means it needs a SDA and SCL line to communicate with the arduino and WiFi network. The servo, encoder, and arduino are powered by a 9V battery. It is stepped down by a power regulator.

Figure 20: Motor 1 Electronic Setup

In the following figure, Figure 21 shows the electronic setup of motor 2. The encoder follows a series of outputs to tell the angular position. This is communicated by pin 7 and 8. The software on the arduino will help decode the encoder output to get a angular position from the client model. The servo, encoder, and arduino are powered by a 9V battery. It is stepped down by a power regulator.

Figure 21: Motor 2 Electronic Setup

In the following figure, Figure 22 shows the electronic setup of motor 3. The encoder and stepper motor are tied together. To communicate to the stepper motor and get the encoder data,

there is a stepper motor driver. The stepper motor drive is connected through a series of wires to the arduino and stepper motor. All the negative lines go to pin 7. All the positive lines go to pin 8. The A and B lines go towards the stepper motor. There is a 9V battery that powers the arduino and wall power to power the stepper motor driver.

Figure 22: Motor 3 Electronic Setup

4.4 Software Manufacturing

The software manufacturing for CROACS was comprised of building our onboard computer, accessing the data from the LiDAR sensor, and connecting our different computational modules. In regards to building the onboard computer, there was nothing of notable challenge besides waiting for all the parts to be delivered and buying any miscellaneous pieces. Once everything was at our disposal, the actual construction of the computer took less than a day.

The largest portion of the software manufacturing was connecting the LiDAR sensor to our onboard computer. This process was streamlined thanks in part to the Analog Devices Software Development Kit (SDK). The SDK was implemented through the Analog Devices GitHub page. In order to access images from the LiDAR, several dependencies were needed to be installed, including CMake, Glog, and Open CV, among others. With the dependencies installed, access to LiDAR came in the form of a demo application, created by Analog Devices, which allows the user to test out the camera to get a sense of its functionality. In order to streamline data, code provided through the SDK was needed to be manipulated.

Although finding where to download the SDK was easy, the steps involved in actually building the SDK offered several challenges. The first and most difficult challenge was actually building the SDK. The Analog Device GitHub page is not very easy to navigate for anyone who is unfamiliar with building environments or new to software development in general. Unfortunately, not many people on our software team were experienced in this field. We would encounter several errors when trying to install the SDK and we could not find the answers easily. Thankfully, contacting the Analog Device engineers was very easy and they answered quickly and efficiently. With their help, the SDK was successfully built.

The next challenge stems from our inability to access a Linux system before the onboard computer was built. In order to have a better understanding of working on a Linux system, a virtual environment was used for the initial weeks of the spring semester. Through the virtual environ-

ment was our first successful build of the SDK. Unfortunately, the SDK was unable to physically connect with the sensor via USB connection due to the virtual environment. This resulted in the team having to wait until the computer arrived and was functional before connecting to the LiDAR and gathering images.

4.5 Integration

All of the components have to be integrated with each other, and as such many of the components were grouped into subsystems. The subsystems include the motor 1 system, the L-arm/motor 2 system, and the stand/motor 3 system, as well as the enclosure. After completing the fabrication of the components, electronics were mounted and integrated to them. Lastly the software was installed and downloaded onto the appropriate components.

4.6 Manufacturing Challenges

The main challenges in the manufacturing portion of the project apply mainly to scheduling. When the original manufacturing timeline was made, the team was extremely optimistic about how long certain things may take. This gave us mere days to finish large portions of the fabrication. In reality, this fabrication took many days and weeks to accomplish. There was immediate schedule setbacks due to the 2 week remote start at the beginning of the semester. This caused many teammates to not be present and manufacturing was initiated by only 2 members of the team.

Other challenges included not receiving many ordered components until much later in the semester, lead times in the machine shop, and unforeseen material complications caused by fabrication methods.

5 Verification and Validation

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5.1 Design Verification

5.1.1 Testing Scope

Level	Test	Model/Process Validated	Equipment/Facilities
Component	Client Motors Client Communications	Datasheet WiFi UDP Protocol	Camera, Tape, Arduinos Arduinos, Motors, Encoders
Subsystem Testing	Servicer Software Identification	Software Flowchart	Servicer, Model, Rangefinder
Comprehensive Testing	Client System Testing Day in the Life	WiFi UDP Protocol Software Flowchart	Vicon, Client Client and Servicer System, Light Fixture

Table 3: Overview of CROACS Testing Scope

CROACS's design has been tested through the system engineering process, beginning with the individual component level test and working up to the full system day in the life test. Each of the component and subsystem tests is used to verify and reduce the risk for the day in the life test. Each test was designed to test the performance of a component/subsystem before the following system can be performed. Not all components/subsystems can be tested thoroughly based on the time and budget constraints. Based on the design of the project and the critical project elements, the client motor and client communications were tested first. Then, the client electronics software integration and servicer ID software were tested. Once these were verified, the comprehensive test with the client vicon system test and day in the life testing was verified. Table 3 shows the individual test, model, and process to validate, and the equipment needed to conduct the test. All of these tests are built on top of each other to validate the most crucial and difficult project objectives.

5.1.2 Client Motors

To make sure that the client is able to move in $10 \frac{deg}{s}$ for the project's level of success, the actuators of the client motor needs to be able to move the client at least $10 \frac{deg}{s}$. Thus, the client motor test was devised.

Figure 23: Client Motor Test Setup

This test is devised by setting up each servo and motor individually. The servos need their respective arduinos and the motor need its compatible driver and arduino. These other components help understand the commands for which the servos and motor is able to actuate to. A protractor is then placed on the center point of the actuator to know the angular rate that which it is rotating. A camera is setup faced perpendicular to the protractor's plane. While the servos and the motor actuates the protractor, the camera is video recording the spin. This test takes place for one minute for multiple trials. These video are then post processed to look at the angular rate that it rotates and the time to determine if the servos and motor can actuate the client body at $10 \frac{deg}{s}$.

In the following figure, Figure 24 shows the test being conducted. In a 1.5 second frame, the client model would move 350 degrees. This means that the client was moving $230 \frac{deg}{s}$. This is faster than the requirement of $10 \frac{deg}{s}$. The initial analysis concluded that the test proved the model

can go from $10 \frac{deg}{s}$. However from future testing with the servos, the servos don't lose the torquing power at low speeds. Unfortunately, this came in the later stages of the design and the team could not buy a better servos to replace it. For future development of the client servos, it is possible to move the servos slower by implementing a PID controller. This was not implement for the current state of the project because of time constraints.

Figure 24: Client Motor Model Test

5.1.3 Client Communication

One of the biggest points of failure of the client design is the communication system. Because the Arduinos in the system need to have bi-lateral communication, wires or a wireless protocol needs to be established. The client's design does not have slip rings so a wired design would break the current stand. Therefore a wireless protocol needs to be verified for the more test the client can go on. As a result, the team used a WiFi protocol to the Arduinos from a remote laptop.

Figure 25: Client Software Test Setup

This test needs the Arduinos WiFi Rev 2 with encoders, actuators, router, and laptop. The encoder reads the position state of the actuators. The encoders send this information to the Arduinos which is then communicated to the router via a WiFi signal. The router then broadcasts the encoder data to the laptop. Next, the laptop can uplink the new command to the Arduino for it to actuate the actuators. Figure 25 is the diagram that explains the test. This test is a component test for WiFi communications. This does not verify the encoder data or actuator commands. The verification of the actuator commands and encoder is done in the client system test. This test is to see if the WiFi communication is fast enough to not induce aliasing for the encoder data. This test also verifies that data can be bi-laterally communicated between the Arduinos and laptop.

Figure 26: WiFi Communication Time with Outliers

Figure 27: WiFi Communication Time without Outliers

Results	Z-Score at 50ms	Percent of Trials <50ms
With Outliers	1.51	93.5%
No Outliers	8.76	100%

Figure 28: WiFi Statistics

Figure 27 shows the results of the test with the averages and standard deviation. Figure 28 shows the statistics on the tests at the 50ms mark. To give context to the test, the histogram shows the uplink and downlink of the WiFi protocol on the y-axis. The x-axis shows the time in milliseconds for the time to go from uplinking the command to downlinking the encoder data. Figure

27 shows the histogram without any outliers. Comparing the figures with and without the outliers show a lot of points being cut from the data set.

Looking at different outlier techniques, the quartiles method was used to remove the outliers from the data set. Looking at the mean method and the robust medium method, the quartiles method was a good compromise between removing lots of points like the robust medium method and removing too few points like the mean method. However, the mean method was not considered because the robust medium method is a mathematical better method than the mean method while the mean method is used for faster computation. Therefore the quartiles method was used because of the compromise.

To ensure that there was no aliasing coming from the WiFi protocol, 50ms was needed from the majority of the trials. Looking at Figure 28, shows the z-score at the 50ms mark. The second column of that table shows the area under the curve for a one-sided normal distribution. With the outliers in the data set, statistically, 93.5% of the trials are under 50ms. That is not perfect because in some cases, there will be aliasing. However, if the outliers are removed from the data set, then, statistically, all of the trials are under 50ms. This is the pass criteria and this test verifies the WiFi protocol. and the client electronics/software integration test can then proceed.

5.1.4 Servicer Software Identification

The Servicer Software Identification test served as the preliminary test of the software architecture up until the post-processing module. This test would feed in LiDAR data through the noise reduction, background differentiation, and template matching algorithms. This test aims to verify the following design requirements:

- DR 1.3: The sensor suite shall be able to gather data from the client at a range of at least 3 m.
- DR 1.4: The sensor suite shall have a range accuracy of at least 10 cm.

- DR 2.1: The software algorithm shall identify the known client from its background.

The test was conducted with the client system, the servicer system, and a laser range finder. The client system will be held stationary for translation and rotation. The servicer system will be placed at three distances (1 m, 2 m, 3 m) while being held at one orientation. For each distance, the servicer will scan the client and send the data to the onboard computer. At this stage, the results of the background differentiation and template matching can be evaluated. To verify the position/distance measurements, the laser range finder is used as truth data. An example of the physical test setup can be found in Figure 29.

Figure 29: Servicer Software Identification Setup

The preliminary results of this test can be found in Figure 30. Without any processing at all, the LiDAR is able to separate the client from its attached motor arms. This initial separation is due to the motor arms and client stand being painted black in order to reduce its reflectivity.

(a) Image of Client

(b) Point Cloud of Client

Figure 30: Preliminary Scans of Client from LiDAR

Upon gathering the point cloud of the client, the data was then sent through our pre-processing module, which includes our noise reduction and background differentiation steps. The results of this module can be seen in Figure 31. This point cloud shows very strong correlation to the client image beside it. The shape of both are very similar and the boosters are recognizable in the point cloud. From this alone, we can say that we have satisfied DR 2.1. Unfortunately, other features of the client, such as the ridges and smaller additions, were no recognizable within the point cloud. This, along with other data quality issues will be discussed and presented thoroughly in Appendix B, Section 10.2.

Figure 31: Pre-Processing Results from Identification Test

The results from the distance portion of the software identification can be found in Table 4. The true distance is measured from the laser range finder with its given uncertainty, while the estimated distance is average centroid measurement from the point cloud frames in the given trial. The table also includes the associated relative error and accuracy from the trails. With the distances that were able to be measured (1.02 m, 2.02 m, 2.82 m), the accuracy fell below the required 10 cm as stated in DR 1.4.

True Distance [m]	Estimated Distance [m]	Relative Error	Accuracy [cm]
1.02 ± 0.05	1.03	1.696%	1.73 ± 5
2.02 ± 0.05	2.01	0.411%	0.89 ± 5
2.82 ± 0.05	2.78	1.294%	3.65 ± 5
3.02 ± 0.05	-	-	-

Table 4: Software Identification Distance Test Results

Unfortunately, one of the biggest obstacles with this project was the LiDAR's Software Development Kit (SDK). In order to regain access to the sensor, a software update was needed to be implemented, which resulted in unforeseen errors that limited our testing capabilities. One such error was the inability to scan past 3 meters. Whenever we tried to access the far mode of our sensor (3 m to 6 m scanning), fatal errors would be thrown that could not be resolved by our team. As of this writing, the engineers at Analog Devices have yet to determine the cause of this error. In

regards to DR 1.3, we are unable to scan at that 3 meters given the current state of our LiDAR, but once the error is determined and a viable solution is presented, we believe that the LiDAR will be able to scan at 3 meters while maintaining that 10 centimeter accuracy.

Along with a discussion of the quality of our point cloud data, the attitude results from this distance test can be found in Appendix B, Section 10.2.

5.1.5 Client System Test

Since the servicer software results were going to be compared to the data captured on board the client, the encoders used to capture this data needed to be verified to ensure their outputs were correct. In addition, the integration of the client electronics and hardware needed to be tested so that any problems with the system could be resolved before "Day in the Life" testing. To achieve this, the Vicon Motion Capturing Software, located in the ASPEN lab at CU Boulder, was used. The Vicon software utilizes 24 infrared cameras that track highly reflective markers that are placed on a desired object. Accurate to less than a millimeter per camera, the Vicon software outputs a .csv file containing three-axis linear and rotational position of the object being tracked throughout the duration of the test. The Vicon data was treated as pure truth data, and the pass criteria for this test was that each encoder was able to estimate angular velocity to within $2[deg/sec]$. To prepare the Vicon system for testing, a coordinate frame was chosen for the client so that each principle axis corresponded to a motor. Seen in the figure below on the left, Motor 1 rotated the client about the X-axis, Motor 2 rotated the client about the Z-axis, and Motor 3 rotated the client about the Y-axis. Then, the Vicon tracking cameras were calibrated and the object was defined within the software. To define the client object within the software, seven markers were placed on the client so that its general shape was represented. The markers, which show up in the software once placed in the field of view of the cameras, were selected so that a coordinate frame for the object could be defined in the software. The object created to track the client can be seen in the figure

below to the right.

(a) Coordinate System for Vicon Test

(b) Client Object as Seen by Vicon Software

After setups of the Vicon and client systems were complete, and the motor(s) had the desired commands uploaded, the motor(s) were commanded to begin rotation, and the encoders began collecting data, both while the team simultaneously started data capture for the Vicon software. Each test run had a duration of approximately 60 seconds. The team captured and used data that was taken only while the client was operating at steady state. This was done to mitigate errors in time-syncing data after the test and because transient data was not as important to this project. After the test runs were completed, the data from the encoders and the Vicon system needed to be aligned for later comparison. As seen in the raw encoder data below to the left, the encoder captured data for periods of one rotation - 360 degrees - then cycled back to the beginning. Since the overall slope of each data set was going to be compared, the team manually aligned this encoder data so that it would be continuous. To do this, each cycle was moved down so that the n th cycle would be moved down by $n * 360$. This resulted in the continuous plot of encoder data shown below on the right.

Figure 33: Data Output From Encoder

Figure 34: Manually Aligned Encoder Data

After the encoder data was aligned, the slope of the best fit curve of to the data was found using the "polyfit" function in MATLAB. This produced the angular velocity captured by the encoders. Then, the same function was used to find the slope of the best fit line of to the Vicon data, producing the angular velocity as seen by the Vicon system. The difference of the two angular velocities was for trials that ran each motor individually. The result was the absolute error for each encoder and whether each encoder met the pass criteria. Shown below is the result of this test for the encoder

for Motor 1. In the plot on the left, the encoder data is plotted, in red, over the Vicon data, both showing angular position over time. The table on the right shows that the Motor 1 encoder was able to satisfy the pass criteria and be reliable during "Day in the Life" testing. However, it's important to note that the data used in the test for Motor 1 was taken at a high speed. This was because the data taken at lower speeds was corrupted.

(a) Motor 1 Encoder Vs Vicon

(b) Motor 1 Encoder Vs Vicon Table

Figure 35: Motor 1 Vicon Verification Results

Similar to Motor 1, the results of the test for the Motor 2 encoder are shown below. However, in the plot on the right, there is the addition of the linear fit of the encoder data, shown in blue. Also like Motor 1, the test for Motor 2 showed that its encoder meets the pass criteria and could be used during "Day in the Life" testing.

(a) Motor 2 Encoder Vs Vicon

Velocity Data	
Vicon Data: <i>Angular Velocity</i>	-45.9894 deg/sec
Encoder Data: <i>Angular Velocity</i>	-44.0460 deg/sec
Absolute Error:	1.9434 deg/sec
Pass Criteria <i><2 deg/sec</i>	Passed

(b) Motor 2 Encoder Vs Vicon Table

Figure 36: Motor 2 Vicon Verification Results

Finally, the results for the test for Motor 3 are shown below. Like the previous two, the encoder for Motor 3 met pass criteria and could be used during "Day in the Life" testing.

(a) Motor 3 Encoder Vs Vicon

Velocity Data	
Vicon Data: <i>Angular Velocity</i>	-18.6869 deg/sec
Encoder Data: <i>Angular Velocity</i>	-17.5787 deg/sec
Absolute Error:	1.1083 deg/sec
Pass Criteria <i><2 deg/sec</i>	Passed

(b) Motor 3 Encoder Vs Vicon Table

Figure 37: Motor 3 Vicon Verification Results

Given that all three encoders met the pass criteria, the team was able to rely on them during "Day in the Life" testing. In addition, this test helped the team map power levels commanded in the arduino software to desired rotation speeds in Motors 1 and 2. Overall, the result of this test

was that the team was assured the client components were integrated properly and the system was ready for "Day in the Life" testing.

5.1.6 Day in the Life Test

The "Day in the Life" test aimed to be the final round of testing that our system would experience. This test would encompass all aspects of the project and verify all design requirements. Unfortunately, due to unforeseen delays and unexpected errors, the team was unable to accomplish full-scale comprehensive testing. For that reason, the test was conducted with only one-axis of rotation (y-axis), keeping the other two stationary. Figure 38 depicts the coordinate frame of the client with respect to the servicer. This coordinate frame is important for the following discussion of the Day in the Life results.

Figure 38: Servicer Coordinate Frame of Client

The test lasted for approximately 15 seconds and scanned the client at a rate of 4 fps. This frame rate was not what was expected when we first chose our LiDAR. With expecting a frame rate of 20 fps, this significant decrease was believed to be caused by an internal software update that issued a distortion correction on the lens. Our team believes that an error is occurring that is

causing the correction to happen twice, which drastically reduces our frame rate. To avoid aliasing, we commanded our client system to rotate at speeds of $[0, 2, 0]$ degrees per second about the x-axis, y-axis, and z-axis respectively. The initial orientation of the client was set to $[0, 0, 0]$ degrees, which can be seen in Figure 38.

The results from this test can be found in Figures 39 through 41. Each figure contains the estimate angles, encoder data, and the best fit line with 1 standard deviation. It is important to note that for both the x- and z-axes, there was no encoder data being taken as those axes were held stationary, so the encoder data was manually set at zero. Figures 39 and 41 do show a strong correlation to the velocity of the respective axis, but not to the angle of that axis. This problem stems from the first frame of the data capture, where our system estimates the initial orientation and uses that for the next estimate. In this test, our software got both the x- and z-axis initial guess wrong, but it was able to maintain that angle within our error bounds. We believe that the initial guess failure stems from the quality of our LiDAR data, which is discussed in Appendix B, Section 10.2.

In regards to Figure 40, which was the lone axis of rotation, shows very promising results. Our attitude estimates show very good behavior that is comparable to the encoder data from the test. The velocity estimates, along with their associated absolute error, can be found in Table 5.

Figure 39: X-Axis Results From LiDAR Scan

Figure 40: Y-Axis Results From LiDAR Scan

Figure 41: Z-Axis Results From LiDAR Scan

In regards to validating our software and the Day in the Life results, simulated data was created. The simulated data is representative of "perfect" data from the LiDAR. No noise and identical to the template database. Upon creating the simulated data, we ran it through our software modules, with the results being found in Figures 42 through 44. With these points, similar to the real data, we have our estimates, truth data from the encoder, and the best fit line with 1 standard deviation. From the figures themselves, all three axes show very strong correlation to the encoder data. Figure 42 does have some notable discrepancies, but this stems from the x-axis being very difficult to detect due to the quality of the point clouds. With our software being verified, the velocities and their associated error can be found in Table 5, along with the results from the real data.

Figure 42: X-Axis Results From Simulated Data

Figure 43: Y-Axis Results From Simulated Data

Figure 44: Z-Axis Results From Simulated Data

Velocity	X-Axis [deg/s]	Y-Axis [deg/s]	Z-Axis [deg/s]
Encoder (Truth)	0	1.954	0
Real	2.086	1.588	-0.794
Real Absolute Error	2.086	0.366	0.794
Simulated	-0.109	1.907	-0.016
Simulated Absolute Error	0.109	0.047	0.016

Table 5: Day in the Life Test Results

6 Risk Assessment and Mitigation

Authors: Shawn Stone, Zack Hubbard

In order for the project to run smoothly, and in order to achieve our desired levels of success, an understanding of the most critical risks was needed during the conceptual design phase of the project. The following section will discuss the anticipated risks, the likelihood at which they were thought to occur, and the severity of the consequences they produced. Further, mitigation meth-

ods used to reduce these occurrences and their consequences will be introduced, along with the resulting impacts on project success.

6.1 Risk Table

Shown below in Table 6 were the 7 most critical risks to the success of the project, in descending order. The risks with the most severe consequences are those that impact overall functional requirements or levels of success, such as an excessive software runtime (R1), the radial symmetry issue (R2), noisy LIDAR data (R3), and overshooting the budget (R7).

Table 6: Risk Table

Number	Description	Effect	Likelihood of Occurrence	Severity of Consequence	Risk Priority Number (RPN)
R1	Excessive software runtime	Predictions become useless	4	5	20
R2	Feature detection can't distinguish unique elements about radial symmetry of client	Failure to determine attitude state	4	5	20
R3	LIDAR data is too noisy to provide necessary detail at far range (3m+)	Unusable point cloud data	3	5	15
R4	Motors dont provide sufficient torque to rotate body about their respective axes at low speeds	Failure of client rotation about one or more axes	3	4	12
R5	Magnetic effects from spinning motors skews truth data measurements	Failure to provide accurate truth data	3	3	9
R6	Interfacing failure between client measurement sensors	Failure to provide truth data	2	4	8
R7	Budget exceeds \$5000	Failure to continue production	1	5	5

Overshooting the budget clearly imposes the consequence of being unable to continue with any manufacturing, product acquisition, and even testing. The software related risks (R1, R2, and R3) generally all have the consequence of limiting the ability of the servicer to perform its core function of characterizing the attitude and movement of the client, albeit in different ways. The other risks,

namely R4, R5, and R6, while not trivial, their consequences are less severe and only impact lower level design requirements or only part of a functional requirement.

6.2 Initial Risk Matrix

The risks outlined previously were then put into a matrix, shown below in Figure 45, which more clearly indicates how acceptable (or rather unacceptable) each risk is.

Figure 45: Initial Risk Matrix

As can be seen, R1 through R3 are well within the unacceptable region, whereas the rest fall under the tolerable category.

6.3 Mitigated Risk Matrix

The mitigation methods to be implemented are listed below:

- R1:** Parallel computing and algorithm optimization (reduces likelihood of occurrence)
- R2:** Algorithm can determine other parameters with missing euler angle (reduces severity) and higher fidelity CAD model with ridges and extra features can be used for software testing (reduces likelihood of occurrence)
- R3:** Algorithm can determine attitude well with noisy data (reduces severity). Lower reflectivity of client rotation stand and/or increased power provided to LIDAR lasers (reduces likelihood)
- R4:** Using gearing to run motors faster at low speeds (reduces severity)
- R5:** Determine bias from Vicon testing, provide truth data from multiple sources, namely IMU and encoders (reduces severity)
- R6:** Use different interfacing methods, like switching from hardwire to BT or vice versa (reduces severity)
- R7:** Finding alternate sources for same components (reduces likelihood)

These mitigation methods result in the following mitigated risk matrix, shown below in Figure 46.

Figure 46: Mitigated Risk Matrix

As can be seen, the mitigation methods pull the most critical risks out of the unacceptable region into the tolerable region, and also reduce the other tolerable risks even further. As for the impact these methods have on the project, most involve increased design and development time, but have largely been accounted for in the project timeline. This includes increased timeline for software development, a redesign of motor 3 to use a gearbox, and bluetooth connections for the truth data.

6.4 Risk Impact on Project Success

Looking back at the risks outlined during the conceptual portion of the project, it is clear that the identification of critical risks was very accurate. Excessive software runtime, radial symmetry of the client, and data capture at far range were the major issues encountered during the later stages

of development. While mitigation methods for these risks, outlined previously, were implemented, these risks did ultimately end up reducing the overall success levels of the project. As for risks R4 through R7, mitigation methods were successfully implemented and ultimately led to avoidance of project failures or partial failures. While not a complete success, the process of risk assessment implemented during the conceptual design phase no doubt contributed to higher overall levels of success for the project.

7 Project Planning

Authors: Tyler Gaston, Jianai Zhao

The most important part of the project plan is a good team structure. The figure below shows how we coordinated our team. For the spring, the project was manufacturing and software intensive, larger sub-teams in these portions were constructed.

Figure 47: Team Organization Chart

Figure 48 shows a work breakdown structure outlining the high level tasks that were to be accomplished for this project. All Project tasks have all been completed. The work products were determined by the project needs and the class requirements.

Figure 48: CROACS Work Breakdown Structure - May 2021

The chart below shows a Gantt timeline of the main WBS tasks. Important milestones are listed at the top with their dates.

Figure 49: CROACS Work Plan - Gantt

The table below shows all of our testing details during the spring semester.

Test Name	Starting Date	Ending Date	Location	Testing Started	Testing Completed
Component Testing	11/30/2021	2/2/2022			
Encoders	1/26/2022	1/28/2022	Aero N200	✓	✓
Client Motors	1/25/2022	2/15/2022	Aero N200	✓	✓
Arduinos	1/28/2022	2/2/2022	Aero N200	✓	✓
Servicer Stand	1/20/2022	2/15/2022	Aero N200	✓	✓
Servicer Enclosure	1/18/2022	2/6/2022	Aero N200	✓	✓
Client Structures	1/24/2022	2/23/2022	Aero N200	✓	✓
Lidar Sensor	11/30/2021	1/21/2022	Aero N200	✓	✓
Client Model	2/1/2022	2/4/2022	Aero N200	✓	✓
Client Communications	2/2/2022	2/21/2022	Aero N200	✓	✓
Subsystem Testing	1/1/2022	3/6/2022			
Client Hardware	2/7/2022	3/6/2022	Aero N200 / Machine Shop	✓	✓
Client Electronics	2/7/2022	3/6/2022	Aero N200 / Aspen Lab	✓	✓
Servicer Hardware	2/7/2022	3/6/2022	Aero N200	✓	✓
Servicer Electronics	2/7/2022	3/6/2022	Aero N200	✓	✓
Servicer Software	1/1/2022	3/20/2022	Aero N200	✓	✓
Client Software	1/26/2022	2/28/2022	Aero N200	✓	✓
Comprehensive Testing	3/7/2022	4/6/2022			
Client System Testing	3/7/2022	4/11/2022	Aero N200	✓	✓
Servicer System Testing	3/7/2022	4/8/2022	Aero N200	✓	✓
Day in the Life Testing	3/21/2022	4/27/2022	Aero N200	✓	✓

Figure 50: CROACS Testing Schedule

The following figure is the financial information. The team found a used LiDAR which decreased our cost significantly. The project total spent is \$3340.31, and this project has \$1459.69 leftover. From expenses percentage chart, the electronics system costs the majority of project budget, spending more money than previous predicted. However, according to all tracked spending's, everything is under control.

Figure 51: Project Financial Charts

8 Lessons Learned

Authors: Nick Herrington, Shawn Stone, Tyler Gaston

8.1 Project Management and Systems Engineering

As a team and as a project, CROACS was largely successful in achieving its desired levels of success, however there are still many lessons learned and key takeaways that would have improved project design and development.

At a project management level, the biggest lessons learned were how to assign team skills and match ambition to project goals. At the start of the project the team was very ambitious outside of our individual strengths. This mismatch led us to have to work harder to meet our initial concepts. Secondly, we found that progress tracking was vital for our software team, and while helpful for manufacturing it was somewhat an exercise for practice and not very useful. Lastly, a big lesson was learned about how to divide up sub teams and work for a small project team of 11 people. We had challenges of complexity that limited our teamwork throughout the semester, which could of

been avoided.

At a systems engineering level, the risks identified in the conceptual design phase of this project were very accurately identified, and despite implementing substantial mitigation methods, it is clear that the project would have benefited from more robust mitigation methods. This would have necessitated an increase in the quantity of methods available for any given risk, and also the depth to which these methods could solve each risk.

Despite best intentions, it was also very clear that the detailed requirements developed for this project in the design portion in the fall semester were not specific enough and did not include enough technical performance measures to be verified and validated properly during the testing phase in the spring semester. This led to difficulties in tracking progress, defining project success, as well as determining the important results to share with the customer and PAB.

8.2 Software Development

8.2.1 Operating System

In order to conserve server hardware resources, it was decided early on that the server would use a lightweight, Linux Debian based operating system. The Lubuntu OS that we selected proved somewhat temperamental to work with because it was not as stable or as frequently maintained as more popular, more user-friendly linux distributions. Some issues included a need to launch in recovery mode and then restart every time the computer was turned on, inability to enable either wifi or ethernet drivers, and a confusing interface to team members less experienced with Linux operating systems. During the course of development it became clear that these trade-offs were not worth the extra time it took to debug and that our server hardware was robust enough to handle our program in a fully fleshed-out Ubuntu consumer environment. The software team eventually rebuilt the environment from scratch after switching to Ubuntu v18.

8.2.2 File Structure

Though the project was contained in a project folder, there were some instances during project development where team members were unaware of the existence and/or inclusion of certain code modules in the program. This in combination with some confusion with lack file structure and nomenclature conventions led to some code modules not being included in the version control, and to occasional bugs where a team member had used the wrong file name or path in their code, which had to be tediously re-written at every such call. At a certain point it became clear that we needed to organize our program structure and this took some time to do effectively, since the program was already quite large at that point. If the software team had outlined a directory structure for the program at the beginning, it would have been a much quicker process and would have led to fewer headaches during the development process.

8.2.3 Team Accountability

While the software team members did have assigned issues on a shared issue board, as well as a slack bot to check their progress, software tickets were often not completed in the time frame required. I think that a regular scrum meeting and more regular software team meetings to work on programming would have been beneficial to completing the tickets in a more timely manner.

8.3 Design Choices

Speaking specifically to the design choices made throughout the project, a few key takeaways were recognized.

Firstly, in regards to LIDAR, it is difficult to accurately assess the COTS solutions that are available on the market. Not only are traed metrics not consistent between products, but LIDAR is also a technology that has the potential for millions of different applications, therefore finding an optimal solution for this project in a relatively niche environment was a difficult task. Many avail-

able LIDAR solutions were designed for use in a completely different industry (such as driverless cars), or had far too broad of application to be useful with our required level of detail. That being said, LIDAR as a whole was found to be very robust in variable lighting conditions and generally proved to be a useful tool as a tracking and state estimation tool.

Secondly, it was determined that future designs would benefit from leveraging multiple LIDAR angles, in combination with a more detailed software algorithm, to make more accurate predictions. Just as the difference between mono and stereo camera systems, increasing the sensing capability of the servicer system would result in more accurate determination of the client object.

Lastly, the client system as a whole that was developed for this project was found to be a very useful and robust tool for testing our software algorithms. It is extremely adaptable to different tumbling scenarios and can be programmed to a wide range of orientations and speeds. This system could prove to be very useful for future testing of this project, or of completely different projects entirely.

9 Individual Report Contributions

Individual Report Contributions	
Name	Contributions
Tyler Gaston	Project planning and Project Manager Responsibilities. Team organization, and proof reading.
Shawn Stone	Risk Assessment and Mitigation section. Part of Lessons Learned section. Rewriting and editing of project purpose and conceptual design sections. General editing and organization.
Brandon diLorenzo	Final Design of Software, Software Manufacturing, Verification and Validation for Software and Day in the Life Tests
Nicholas Herrington	Lesson Learned, Main Document Outline
Jash Bhalavat	Detailed Design of Client Electronics, Verification and Validation
Jason Le	Final Design of Electronics, Electronics Manufacturing, Verification and Validation for Electronics, General Edits
Max Morgan	Objectives and Functional Requirements, Conceptual Design of Servicer Electronics
Jake Pirnack	Conceptual Design of Client hardware (truth data), Verification and Validation for all component, sub-system, and system levels, Detail Design for Servicer hardware
Walter Sabin	Conceptual design of Client hardware, Detailed design of Client Hardware, cohesive edits to Conceptual Servicer System design
Zackary Hubbard	Servicer Hardware, Client Hardware, Client Electronics, Risk Analysis, Manufacturing
Jianai Zhao	Project purpose, Project Objectives and Functional Requirements, and part of Project Planning

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10 Appendices

10.1 Appendix A: Conceptual Design

10.1.1 Overall Conceptual Design

As a whole, the conceptual design portion of CROACS involved considering as many design alternatives as possible within each subsystem of the project. For the sake of brevity, the in-depth research, descriptions, trade metrics, and other information is omitted from the following section, and is included in Appendix A, starting on page 68. A summary, listing each of the alternatives and their pros and cons will instead be shown, followed by the results of the trade study and the chosen baseline design solution.

Servicer Software *Contributor(s): Brandon diLorenzo, Nicholas Herrington, Shawn Stone
Various pose determination algorithms were researched and traded in order to determine the best techniques for determining attitude, position, velocity, and angular velocity. These are listed below in Table 7, with their pros and cons. A more detailed look at each of these alternatives, including the chosen metrics and their weightings, can be found starting on page 102 in Appendix A.

Table 7: Conceptual Design Alternatives for Servicer Software Algorithms

Algorithm	Pros	Cons
Passive Pose Acquisition: Shape-from-Shading	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires less detail than 3D • Computationally efficient • Requires only one image 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower resolution • Not as accurate as 3D • Dependent on lighting conditions
Passive Pose Acquisition: Shape-from-Texture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires less detail than 3D • Computationally efficient • Requires only one image 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower resolution • Not as accurate as 3D • Requires unique textures
Active Pose Acquisition: 3D Online Template Matching	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More Precise Matching • Well Documented 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computationally Expensive • Exclusively LiDAR
Active Pose Acquisition: 3D PCA Online Template Matching	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less Templates for Comparison • Computationally Efficient 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Orientation Issues (additional algorithm) • Exclusively LiDAR
Passive Pose Tracking: Edge-tracker	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computationally Efficient • Online or Offline 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not robust • Needs previous templates of known object
Active Pose Tracking: Iterative Closest Point	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accurate and Robust • Highly compatible with LiDAR and stereo camera 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computationally expensive • Dependent on initial estimation and relative dynamics
Active Pose Tracking: Absolute Orientation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accurate and Robust • Computationally inexpensive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only compatible with LiDAR • Dependent on initial estimation and relative dynamics

Following the research of these alternatives, two trade studies were conducted, whose results are shown below in Figure 52.

Category	Weight	Shape-from-Shading	Shape-from-Texture	3D Online TM	3D PCA Online TM
Complexity	0.3	3	3	2	2
Accessibility	0.2	5	4	3	4
Acquisition Accuracy	0.3	3	1	5	3
Light Dependence	0.2	1	1	5	5
TOTAL	1	3	2.2	3.7	3.3

Figure 52: Trade Matrix of Pose Acquisition

Category	Weight	Iterative Closest Point	Absolute Orientation
Complexity	0.3	3	3
Accessibility	0.2	4	3
Acquisition Accuracy	0.3	4	5
Light Dependence	0.2	5	5
TOTAL	1	3.9	4

Figure 53: Trade Matrix of Active Pose Tracking

Client System *Contributor(s): Zack Hubbard, Shawn Stone, Walter Sabin

The FR 5 states, "A client object shall be created for algorithm testing and demonstration". Further, the client needs to spin at 10 degrees/sec in 3 axes simultaneously while collecting data about its rotation. The client resembles a Saturn V rocket body that is 1/82 scaled. The rotation is carried by 3 motors (2 servos and 1 stepper) and their rotation is measured by 3 encoders mounted close to the motors and 1 IMU on the client body. All of this is supported by a custom made stand that allows the rotation. A summary of the design alternatives considered, their resulting trade studies, and baseline design selection are elaborated in the sections below. Again, the more detailed information, including the chosen metrics and their weightings, can be found starting on page 87 in Appendix A.

Modeling Rotational Dynamics of Client Model The rotation of the model needs to be simulated so that different modes of rotation are shown while keeping the client within the view of the

sensor suite. Table 8 below shows the pros and cons to various design alternatives to modeling the rotational dynamics of the physical model.

Table 8: Conceptual Design Alternatives for Rotational Dynamics of Physical Model

Rotational Mechanism	Pros	Cons
Air Table	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frictionless motion • Cost effective and simple • Prolonged test time 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only rotate about one axis • Difficult to achieve precise rotation rates
Stop Motion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quick and easy to implement • Almost unlimited test time • No gimbal lock or other rotation limitations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limits success level (not close to real time) • Human error • Every scenario requires detailed plan of action
3 Axis Motorized Goniometer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accurate rotation positions • Time and resource efficient (COTS) • Simple integration of motors and control system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High cost • Integration risk with physical model and truth data acquisition
Custom 3 Axis Rotating Stand	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adjustable to scale of physical model • Shorter and more predictable shipping for structure of stand (raw materials) • Able to modify and specialize design 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time and resource expensive • Possible inaccuracies in rotation of the model

These design alternatives were then traded by measuring how well each option performed in the categories of variability, controlability, visibility, cost and complexity. Variability is the measure of how many different modes of rotation (different rotational directions and speeds) each option could produce, Controlability is how easily and precisely each mode of rotation would be to simulate repeatedly. Visibility measures how well each option avoids obstructing the sensor suite’s view of the client model. The cost category measures how well each option fits into the budget. Finally

complexity measures how easy each option is to manufacture and operate. The resulting matrix is seen below in Figure 54.

Category	Weight	Air Table	Stop Motion	Goniometer	Custom 3 Axis Rotating Stand
Variability	0.3	1	5	4	5
Controlability	0.15	1	1	4	4
Visibility/Obstruction of Sensor FOV	0.2	5	3	3	3
Cost	0.15	3	4	2	4
Complexity	0.2	5	3	4	3
TOTAL	1	2.9	3.45	3.5	3.9

Figure 54: Trade Matrix of Rotation Model

As can be seen, based on the desired metrics and their weighting, the most viable design solution is a custom 3-axis rotating stand. This solution, along with the motor and truth data design selection, will be discussed later as part of the overall baseline design of the client system in section. The final design of CROACS was selected and refined from the conceptual design element alternatives considered early on in the project.

Motor Selection Since the custom rotating stand is operated remotely, motors were researched in order to provide accurate, consistent rotation to the client model. Each motor needs to have a high enough torque rating in order to smoothly rotate the model. The speed at which the motors operate best was also researched in order to find the best fit. Table 9 below shows the pros and cons to the two design alternatives in regards to motor selection and more detailed descriptions of each motor option can be found in the appendix.

Table 9: Conceptual Design Alternatives for Motor Selection

Rotation Mechanism	Pros	Cons
Continuous Rotation Servos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small size • Ease of implementation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not rated for high torque demands • Low torque at slow speeds
Stepper Motors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability to handle large torque demands • Stronger shaft 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Large/heavy size • Discrete stepped motion at low speeds

Since different aspects of the client system have vastly different torque requirements (explained further in the detailed design) a combination of continuous rotation servos and a stepper was determined to be the best option.

Truth Data To measure the accuracy of the software that is developed, truth data of position and rotation rates will be collected from the client model. Numerous different options were considered for this because the data needs to be accurate, easy to retrieve and compact enough to fit inside the client model. Table 10 below shows the pros and cons to the various design alternatives for the measurement of the truth data from the client system.

Table 10: Conceptual Design Alternatives for Truth Data Acquisition

Truth Data Device	Pros	Cons
Accelerometer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small size • Linear & angular measurements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor angular measurements • Wires interfering with rotation stand
Rate Gyro	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small size • Easy to use 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wires interfering with test stand
Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small size • Measures acceleration and position 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Must be connected via wires • Increased software complexity
Rotary Encoder	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased confidence in measurements • Eliminates obstruction with the debris model 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple sensors needed • Added uncertainty (not directly measuring client)

These alternatives were traded using the categories of fidelity, feasibility, size, and data capture rate. Fidelity measures how accurate and repeatable the data sets from each option are. Feasibility is a measure of how accessible and easy the components of each option are to implement. Size measures how well each option will fit once integrated in to the client system. Finally, data capture rate is used to grade the options because more data points can lead to higher accuracy. The resulting matrix is seen below in Figure 55.

Category	Weight	Accelerometer	Gyroscope	IMU	Rotary encoder
Fidelity	0.3	2	3	4	5
Feasibility	0.25	5	4	5	5
Size	0.2	4	4	4	5
Data Capture Rate	0.25	5	5	5	3
TOTAL	1	3.9	3.95	4.5	4.5

Figure 55: Trade Matrix of Truth Data

Based on the need for high fidelity measurements, fast capture rates, easy of assembly/integration, and size, IMU’s and rotary encoders were tied for the most viable solutions.

Servicer System *Contributor(s): Max Morgan, Shawn Stone, Zack Hubbard

Looking at FR 1 and FR 3, some of the more critical design choices are the sensors and processors used to gather data and run software. The following section outlines the design alternatives that were considered, the resulting trade studies, and the final selection, both for the sensor suite and onboard processor. Once again, the more detailed information, including the chosen metrics and their weightings for the trade studies, can be found starting on page 102 in Appendix A.

Sensor Suite The most critical design choice to make is the type of sensor that will be used to remotely sense the client satellite. The sensor that is chosen needs to output data that can be used to interpret the rotation of the client model. This data needs to be accessible by the team without compromising the data as well as without taking up too much time. In addition to these software requirements, the sensor needs to be able to work in variable lighting and moving situations. Table 11 below shows the pros and cons to various sensors available today.

Table 11: Conceptual Design Alternatives for Sensor Suite

Sensor Suite	Pros	Cons
Stereo Cameras	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collects whole image at once • Wide FOV • Measures visual and distance info 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires ambient light • Computationally expensive • Short to medium range
Monocular Camera	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collects whole image at once • Wide FOV 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires ambient light • Short to medium range • No distance/range information
Scanning LIDAR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Far range • No ambient light required • High range accuracy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collects data line by line • Lower sampling rate • Accuracy depends on reflectivity
Scannerless Continuous-Wave LIDAR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measures movement accurately • No ambient light required • High range accuracy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only measures velocity in one direction • Emerging technology
Scannerless Pulsed LIDAR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collects whole image at once • No ambient light required • High distance accuracy • High sampling rate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expensive • Accuracy depends on reflectivity
Spatial Light Modulating LIDAR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collects whole image at once • No ambient light required • Simple hardware design 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complex software design • Emerging technology

Overall, there are 6 metrics that were chosen to evaluate these technologies, namely, software complexity, hardware complexity, effective range, sensitivity to lighting, data density, and sensitivity to rapid movement. Once again, these alternatives were traded, and resulted in the matrix

shown below in Figure 56.

Category	Weight	Stereo Cameras	Monocular Camera	Scanning LIDAR	Scannerless LIDAR	Spatial Light Modulating LIDAR
Software Complexity (lower is more complex)	0.3	2	1	3	2	1
Hardware Complexity (lower is more complex)	0.1	5	5	2	4	4
Effective Range	0.1	3	3	5	5	3
Sensitivity to Lighting	0.15	1	1	5	5	4
Data Density	0.2	5	4	3	3	5
Sensitivity to Rapid Movement	0.15	5	5	1	5	3
TOTAL	1	3.3	2.8	3.1	3.6	3.05

Figure 56: Trade Matrix of Sensor Technology

Onboard Processor As per FR 3, the servicer system must use an onboard solution for its computations, therefore, alternative design alternatives were researched to determine the most viable solution for the baseline design. Table 12 below shows these design alternatives, along with general pros and cons to each.

Table 12: Conceptual Design Alternatives for Onboard Computing

Sensor Suite	Pros	Cons
Microcontroller	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inexpensive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Weakest overall specifications Restrictive
Low-spec Microcomputer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inexpensive Wide software compatibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Weak processors Not customizable
Mid-spec Microcomputer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cost Effective High memory capacity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not customizable
Pre-built and Internal Graphics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fast processors High memory capacity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not fully customizable
Self-built and Internal Graphics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fastest processor Fastest Memory 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expensive
Self-built and External Graphics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Highest Specs Fully customizable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Very expensive

Once again, these alternatives were traded, with the key metrics being the cost and compatibility of the processor. This trade is shown below in Figure 57.

Category	Weight	Microcontroller	Low-spec Microcomputer	Mid-spec Microcomputer	Pre-built, internal graphics	Self-built, internal graphics	Self-built, external graphics
Cost	0.3	5	5	4	3	2	1
Compatibility	0.3	1	2	2	3	4	5
Processor Speed	0.2	1	2	3	5	5	5
Graphics Speed	0	1	2	3	4	4	5
Memory	0.2	1	1	5	5	5	5
TOTAL	1	2.2	2.7	3.4	3.8	3.8	3.8

Figure 57: Trade Matrix of On-board Processor

Servicer Stand The servicing stand needs to be able to translate 1 meter per customer requirements. The stand also needs to be able to rotate in order to test different linear motion relationships between the servicer and the client. The translation is achieved by using a track the servicer will follow. The servicer will sit atop a center beam connected to the rails with wheels, which will slide along the track. This will provide the desired 1 meter of translational motion. On the top of the center beam will be a seat swivel capable of rotational movement in increments of 30° . This allows the enclosure to be pointed in different directions to get different types of translational motion relationships the servicer may encounter on a mission. This design was chosen to achieve the requirements of the servicer in a simple and functional manner, and so no trade study was conducted on the options as this design maximizes simplicity.

Overall Baseline Design

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The baseline design solution is as follows.

- **Power system:** The user powers on the CROACS system, which draws power from the wall power outlet and is run through the power supply.
- **Client Tumbling System:** The user inputs a scenario which is relayed to the Portenta H7 and Arduino Unos. These activate the servo motors and stepper motors which rotate the client model. The encoders and Nicla Sense IMU measure truth data to send to the Servicer.
- **Servicer System:** The active scanning LiDAR sensor receives information and converts it to a point cloud PLY file. This is then sent to the onboard computer for data processing. The data is bounded and de-noised. 3D online template matching is then used to identify the pose of the client object. ICP methods and edge detection are used to determine the attitude of the client object. A linear regression analysis is then used to determine the client object's change in attitude as a function of time. A best fit function is found that describes the client's behaviour, and that behaviour is then propagated into the future. The current and future state

vector is then output by the program, along with error compared to the truth data from the encoders and IMU.

Figure 58: Full System Baseline Design

The figure above illustrates the CROACS servicer capturing data about the client being rotated by the testing stand.

10.1.2 Servicer Software

10.1.2.1 Conceptual Design Alternatives

10.1.2.1.1 Passive Pose Acquisition: Shape-from-Shading

The orientation of an object's surface is defined by the surface normal at each point on the object. Based on the illumination direction the surface normal of each pixel is found. Since surface reflectivity is a function of the reflected direction and incident direction, and therefore a directional property, where the angle of reflection can be assumed to be equal for diffuse surfaces. This diffusivity assumption is close enough to accurate for the types of objects that will be encountered

on this project. With a fixed illumination direction, the surface normals are only a function of the illumination angle. The object is then constructed from its calculated surface normals.

Pros	Cons
Requires less resolution than 3D	Lower resolution
Computationally efficient	Not as accurate as 3D
Requires only one image	Dependent on lighting conditions

10.1.2.1.2 Passive Pose Acquisition: Shape-from-Texture

Shape-by-texture algorithms utilize repetition and localizability properties of texture elements. Repetition of a texture element means that there must be a portion of the object texture that repeats over the surface of the object. Localizability is the structural uniqueness of the texture element within the image. The algorithm works by first identifying these texture elements, then reconstructing the frontal appearance of each element to fit a scaled orthographic view, then discarding any elements whose frontal appearance lacks adequate slant and tilt estimates.

Pros	Cons
Requires less resolution than 3D	Lower resolution
Computationally efficient	Not as accurate as 3D
Requires only one image	Dependent on lighting conditions
	Requires unique textures

10.1.2.1.3 Active Pose Acquisition: 3D Online TM

3D online template matching (TM) involves comparing LIDAR-generated 3D point clouds to a database of point cloud templates, those of which were created from geometrical information known about the client [?]. Utilizing a 2D or 3D image of the object, a 6 degree-of-freedom template database is formed using range of Euler angles. Once the first LIDAR data is collected, the centroid of the client, which is the main component of comparison, is calculated and treated as the relative position solution. The sensor centroid is then overlapped onto the centroids of the templates in the database to avoid misalignment in matching, followed by matching each sensor

cloud point to the nearest point on the template. A correlation function then calculates the average of the difference between each sensor and template point. The template corresponding to the smallest correlation function value produces the relative attitude solution. This algorithm can be followed in Figure 59.

Figure 59: 3D Online TM Flow Diagram

Creating the database using a variation of all three Euler angles provides a large quantity of templates to compare to, resulting in a more precise matching solution. However, having a sizeable database results in a slower computation time, as the correlation function must go through every template in order to optimize

Pros	Cons
More Precise Matching	Computationally Expensive
Well Documented	Exclusively LiDAR

10.1.2.1.4 Active Pose Acquisition: 3D PCA Online TM

Similar to Section 10.1.2.1.3, 3D principal component analysis (PCA) online template matching, hereby referenced as PCA-TM, uses a template database as a means of comparing LIDAR cloud data. However, this algorithm differs in both the offline and online components. Instead of using all three Euler angles to create the database, PCA-TM only uses the yaw angle to vary the templates. For the online processes, PCA-TM implements primary component analysis to find the orientation of the client’s main axis [4]. The main axis can then be used to find the roll and pitch angles of the client. The yaw angle is found through the template matching as described in 10.1.2.1.3. The PCA-TM algorithm can be found in Figure 60.

Figure 60: 3D PCA Online TM Flow Diagram

One advantage of the PCA-TM algorithm is the template database formation. Using only one Euler angle reduces the number of templates created three-fold when compared to the other template matching algorithm (Section 10.1.2.1.3), which greatly improves the computation speed of the algorithm. However, one major issue that arises from the use of PCA is the orientation of the client’s main axis. From the algorithm, there is no way of determining whether the main axis corresponds to the positive or negative z-axis in the client reference frame. This problem can be solved by implementing another algorithm between acquisition and tracking.

Pros	Cons
Less Templates for Comparison	Orientation Issues
Computationally Efficient	Additional Algorithm
Well Documented	Exclusively LIDAR

10.1.2.1.5 Passive Pose Tracking: Edge-tracker

This method of pose tracking is used for a monocular approach where a set of 2D-to-3D point correspondences are used to estimate the pose parameters. The algorithm develops an edge-image and it requires an initial estimate of the pose parameters to update the client's relative attitude and position. The drawback to this approach is that when the client and chaser are relatively fast, the algorithm breaks down [5]. This algorithm can run online as well as off-line given that images of the client are available from past missions.

Pros	Cons
Computationally cheap	Not robust
Online or Offline	Needs previous templates of known object

10.1.2.1.6 Active Pose Tracking: Iterative Closest Point

The iterative closest point (ICP) algorithm is compatible with a 3D approach which is designed to find an estimate of the optimal rigid transformation necessary to align a client-model point cloud to a dataset acquired with LiDARs or stereo cameras. The effectiveness of this algorithm depends heavily on the initial pose estimate and the chaser-client relative dynamics [6]. In order to speed up the algorithm, pose refinement is also needed. Hence, ICP is computationally heavy, but accurate.

Pros	Cons
Accurate and Robust	Computationally expensive
Highly compatible with LiDAR and stereo camera	Dependent on initial estimation and relative dynamics

10.1.2.2 Trade Studies

Trade Metrics

Four different metrics were considered for acquisition algorithm. Specifically, complexity, accessibility, acquisition accuracy, and light dependence. The driving requirements and rationale for each can be seen in Table 13

Category	Weight	Driving Requirements	Rationale
Complexity	0.3	Project Timeline	Since, this is expected to be a significant portion of the project, it is important to make sure that the algorithm isn't so complex such that it cannot be completed during the course.
Accessibility	0.2	FR 2, DR 2.3	Since this specific field of object sensing is still developing, the solution should be robust for the project's needs yet developed enough to be available to the team.
Acquisition Accuracy	0.3	FR 2, DR 2.2	Acquisition is not the final stage of the pose determination algorithm, but it is important that the acquisition algorithm be as accurate as possible in order to have the remaining portion of the algorithm be computationally efficient
Light Dependence	0.2	DR 1.5	In the space environment, there will be times where little-to-no light will be available for the sensor imaging. It is necessary for the algorithm to be able to function under any lighting conditions

Table 13: Trade Metrics Table with Rationale and Driving Requirements

Figure 73 goes over the criteria for each given metric in the trade study.

Trade Metric Scale

The scale of the trade metrics used to rank each category are shown below in Figure 73.

Metric	1	2	3	4	5
Complexity	The time and resources required to execute the algorithm are far beyond the scope of the course	The algorithm is very difficult to execute. It is not out of the realm of possibility, but will require a significant amount of time to achieve	The algorithm is moderately complex, but reasonable to accomplish in the given project timeline	The algorithm is fairly simple, but there are a few more complicated steps that will take time to solve	The algorithm is not complex at all and very easy to implement into our design
Accessibility	In its initial stages and requires lot of research/development by the team in order to successfully execute	Has been researched and documented but requires development by the team	Research and development are new to the market and scarcely available/tested	Is available in the market but requires abundant learning	Is available in the market with tutorials and is customizable per the team's needs
Acquisition Accuracy	The algorithm has the potential to have significantly inaccurate acquisition	N/A	The algorithm is not completely accurate, but it has the ability to be corrected with additional algorithms	N/A	The algorithm has proven to get close acquisition, resulting in significantly less tracking and refinement computation
Light Dependence	The algorithm is almost completely reliant on light and will fail in certain lighting conditions	N/A	N/A	N/A	The algorithm has no dependence on light and can function in any lighting conditions

Figure 61: Trade Matrix Scale of Pose Determination

Trade Matrix

The trade matrix with the results of the study are shown below in Figure 62.

Category	Weight	Shape-from-Shading	Shape-from-Texture	3D Online TM	3D PCA Online TM
Complexity	0.3	3	3	2	2
Accessibility	0.2	5	4	3	4
Acquisition Accuracy	0.3	3	1	5	3
Light Dependence	0.2	1	1	5	5
TOTAL	1	3	2.2	3.7	3.3

Figure 62: Trade Matrix of Pose Acquisition

10.1.2.3 Baseline Design

The pose determination algorithms presented in the trade study have two acquisition options being compatible with passive sensors and another two acquisition options being compatible with active sensors. With cross-compatibility not being an option, the selection of the algorithm is entirely dependent on the selection of the sensor. In the sensor suite section above, the sensor selected was scannerless LIDAR, which is an active sensor. Looking at the active acquisition algorithms, 3D Online TM and 3D PCA Online TM, in Figure 52, the 3D online template matching is the best option for our design. Our selection of this algorithm stems from a few key reasons. First, 3D Online TM has a vast amount of templates to match to, allowing for a more precise matching to the sensor cloud. Although this algorithm might not be as accessible as 3D PCA Online TM, it scores higher in the accuracy spectrum which has a higher weight. Hence, the trade-off is more research and development for the team, but it should result in a more accurate solution. In regards to the pose tracking, the algorithm selected was the Iterative Closest Point (ICP) algorithm. As there are not many other pose tracking algorithms for active sensors, no trade study was conducted.

10.1.3 Client System

10.1.3.1 Conceptual Design Alternatives

10.1.3.1.1 Modeling Rotational Dynamics of Physical Model

Air Table

Air tables are a tool for conducting near frictionless, two dimensional experiments. Since, air tables are near frictionless, they simulate microgravity very well. The client shall be small and able to rotate freely on the table. It shall contain a sensor that can record the rotation of the client. Also, since, it doesn't require motors, motion shall be actuated by hands. However, this rotation can only be conducted in 1 axis and it also requires the servicer to be place on top of the table. This restricts the translation motion of the servicer which is another requirement set forth by the customer.

Pros	Cons
Frictionless motion	Only rotate about one axis (perpendicular to surface of table)
Cost effective and simple	Can't achieve precise rotation rates
Prolonged test time	Possible weight restrictions of model

Stop Motion

If the client is rotated by hand with intervals in between, the algorithm can perceive it as continuous motion. This is possible if the sensor is only exposed to the client after it changes its attitude. Then, the sensor is paused and the team manually changes the attitude and the cycle goes on. This is cheap and does not require any electrical connection except a sensor inside to model to accurately collect truth data. The team will manually input the time variable and will have control over how fast the software is perceiving the client. This allows simulation of almost any tumbling mode and is quick and easy to use. However, this decreases the level of success of the algorithm and can lead to inaccuracies because the client is rotated manually.

Pros	Cons
Quick and easy to use	Limits success level of algorithm
Almost unlimited test time	Risk of inaccuracies in change in angle between stops
Can simulate almost all tumbling modes	Requires a detailed plan to create the stop motion

3 Axis Motorized Goniometer

A goniometer is an off the shelf tool that can be used to rotate an object to a precise angle. In this project, three goniometers would be configured with motors so that the model could be rotated about three axes simultaneously without human intervention. An example of this device is shown in figure 63 below. The off the shelf aspect of this option would save time in designing, and would be relatively easy to set up given that motors are supposed to be integrated and sometimes even included in the product. The rotation of the object would also be relatively accurate as off the shelf goniometers can have resolutions of down to less than 0.5° [7]. However, one disadvantage of using this device would be the cost. Given that this project would require a type of goniometer which is essentially a combination of three, single axis, rotation stages, the cost can easily exceed \$1,000. In addition to this high cost, lead times can be lengthy and unpredictable since these devices are high precision, specialized tools. Another disadvantage could be the geometry of these devices. Modifying off the shelf goniometers is not really an option, so, the design of the client model would be heavily constrained. Additionally, this restricts the design of the physical rocket model.

Figure 63: Example of 3 Axis Goniometer

Pros	Cons
Very accurate rotation positions	Very high cost
Save time and resources since goniometer does not have to be designed or manufactured	Lead times could be very long and unpredictable
Easy to integrate motors and control system	Possible difficulty integrating physical model into the goniometer

Custom 3 Axis Rotating Stand

An alternative to an off the shelf goniometer would be to manufacture a custom three axis rotating stand. This would be a very similar principle to the goniometer in that the custom stand would likely consist of three rotating stages that are combined so that an attached object would be able to rotate about three different axes. The test set up for the custom stand would also be very similar to the goniometer because it would rotate the client within the field of view of the sensor suite and truth data would still likely be taken through a sensor within the client. One way the custom stand differs from the off the shelf option would be that the geometry of the stand would be designed in accordance with geometry of the client allowing for a comfortable fit between the stand, the client, and its associated hardware. In addition to this, since the team would be manufacturing the stand, there would not be a waiting period for shipping. Although, motors and possibly some associated electronics may need to be shipped, this would, in general, allow for rapid turnaround

for designing, testing and iterating the concept for the test stand. Some disadvantages of the custom stand would be that the design process will consume time and resources, and some aspects of the stand may come to be very difficult to design or even prove to be impractical. Another disadvantage could be the accuracy of the rotation of the stand. Different orientations and angular velocities may be hard to predict with a custom motor set up. Although, these data will ultimately come from the choice of truth data chosen, it could be helpful to be able to compare truth data with that from the inputs to the stand. Some sketches of possible custom stands are shown below.

Figure 64: Rough Sketches of Possible Custom 3 Axis Rotation Stand Designs

Pros	Cons
Good fit for physical model since stand is designed specifically for this purpose	Requires time and resources to design and manufacture
No wait for shipping for structure of stand	Risk difficult design/manufacturing process
Able to iterate and improve design	Possible inaccuracies in rotation of the model

10.1.3.1.2 Motor Selection

Continuous Rotation Servos

Continuous rotation servos provide rotation about an axis. These are often small and used in situations where the torque demands are not high. Servos are relatively cheap and easy to use, not requiring more than a micro-controller to regulate rotation rate and with small input voltages.

Figure 65: Servo

Pros	Cons
Small size	Not Rated for High Torque Demands
Ease of Implementation	Low Torque at Slow Speeds

Stepper Motors

Stepper motors are a continuous rotation motor dividing the rotation into multiple steps. Stepper motors are driven using an external driver in order to regulate the rotation rate. These motors are able to handle higher torque demands than a servo, however they develop a step type motion when commanded to perform slow rotations.

Figure 66: Stepper

Pros	Cons
Ability to Handle Large Torque Demands	Large/Heavy Size
Stronger Shaft	Stepping Type Motion at Low Speeds

10.1.3.1.3 Truth Data

Accelerometer

By placing an accelerometer on the client debris object it would be possible to obtain not only angular acceleration and velocity, but also transnational acceleration and velocity. However, since angular motion measurements requires post-processing calculations and estimations when using an accelerometer it is best to consider other alternatives that are most specifically designed to measure angular motion.

Images/test options/truth data/accelerometer.jpg

Figure 67: Accelerometer

Pros	Cons
Small size	Poor angular measurements
Linear & angular measurements	Wires interfering with test stand

Rate Gyro

A rate gyro would more accurately measure angular velocities of the model. One downside to this setup is that wires must connect the micro controller to the gyro. This physical connection could get in the way of the rotating model. Wireless connections for micro controllers exist via WiFi and/or Bluetooth, but these features may add cost and complexity to the software side of the system.

Images/test options/truth data/rategyro.jpg

Figure 68: Rate Gyro

Pros	Cons
Small size	Wires interfering with test stand
Easy to use	

Inertial Measurement Unit

An Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) is another sensor that can characterize the rotation of a body. Contrary to a rate gyro, IMUs measure angular acceleration and position. Both of these measurements could be used in combination with the relative change in time to calculate the angular velocity at a given point. Some disadvantages of IMUs could be an increase in complexity of the software used to run the sensor due to an increase in data. IMUs also share a disadvantage with rate gyros in that they must be physically connected to a microcontroller for use which could obstruct the rotation of the physical model.

Figure 69: IMU
[?]

Pros	Cons
Measures acceleration and position	Must be connected via wires
Small in size	Increased software complexity

Rotary Encoder

An alternative approach to achieving truth data of the angular velocity of the client is to use rotary encoders on the test stand itself. This method will only work for select rotating test stand configurations. Instead of attaching a gyro or IMU sensor to the client itself, encoders can be placed on the shafts of any motors used to rotate the object in the test stand. Assuming that the client is fixed in the test stand if the true angular velocity of the motor turning the object is measured than this can also serve as truth data for the angular velocity of the tumbling object. An encoder would be needed for each axis in which the tumbling object is rotating about (1 to 3).

Figure 70: Rotary Encoder
[?]

Pros	Cons
Increased confidence in measurements	Multiple sensors needed
Eliminates obstruction on the debris model	Added uncertainty (not directly)

10.1.3.2 Trade Studies

Modeling Rotational Dynamics of Physical Model

Trade Metrics

Category	Weight	Driving Requirements	Rationale
Variability (DOF)	0.3	DR 1.5; FR 2, DR 2.2; FR 5,	Testing different scenarios will result in a more well rounded test of the algorithm that is developed. The more unique tumbling modes and environments the model can achieve, the more the model will resemble reality. This carries a lot of weight because one of the main goals is to create a robust algorithm that can be easily translated to a real application.
Controllability	0.15	DR 5.1, DR 5.2	A model that can be reliably controlled would allow for more precise tests to be conducted. A more precise control system on the model will allow for a better prediction of what the truth data solution outputs. This could help in simulating scenarios that are similar but may have small differences eg. two tumbling modes that have the same rotational direction but different speeds.
Visibility/Obstruction of Sensor FOV	0.2	DR 1.3, DR 1.5; DR 5.1, DR5.4	A better view of the rotating model will result in a better observation and characterization from the sensor suite/algorithm. An unobstructed view of the rotating debris would also be a more realistic representation.
Cost	0.15	Resources	While many options have feasible prices available, there is still a limited budget that needs to allow for the rest of the project.
Complexity	0.2	Time and Resources	A simple design would be easier to manufacture and test which could keep costs low. This would also save time and allow for more time for testing and possibly iterations on the design of the client model.

Table 14: Rotation Model Trade Metrics Table with Rationale and Driving Requirements

Trade Metric Scale

Metric	1	2	3	4	5
Variability	Only able to rotate target model about one axis.	N/A	Able to rotate target model about 2 different axes.	Able to rotate target model about three different axes.	Able to rotate target model about three different axes with variable speeds.
Controlability	Model must be spun by hand and no real control system can be integrated.	Control system can spin target model and input can match the direction of the rotation presented in the truth data of the model	Control system would be able to be integrated and spin about two different axes with some precision so that inputs somewhat resemble truth data. (Same direction and within approx. 10rpm)	Control system would be able to be integrated and spin target about three different axes with some precision so that inputs somewhat resemble truth data. (Same direction and within approx. 10rpm)	Control system can be integrated and spin target about three different axes at variable speeds with high precision so that it matches truth data.
Visibility/Obstruction of Sensor FOV	Set up consistently obstructs view of target	N/A	Set up could obstruct view of target, but only in certain orientations of the target.	N/A	Set up offers no obstruction at any point in the experiment regardless of orientation of the target.
Cost	Solution costs more than \$5,000 budget or requires more than half of the total budget	Solution would require approximately half of budget	Solution requires significant portion of budget (approx. 30%-40%)	Cost of solution is not negligible but requires less than approximately 30% of budget	Cost of solution would be negligible compared to the budget
Complexity	Solution requires all custom made parts with little to no pre-existing designs to imitate	Solution requires all custom parts but similar solutions exist and can be imitated	Solution requires mostly custom parts with some pre-existing off the shelf parts that can be integrated. Other solutions exist and can be imitated.	Solution requires some custom parts but can be made up of mostly pre-existing off the shelf parts that can be integrated. Other solutions exist and can be imitated.	Solution is bought off the shelf with little to no integration of model/hardware required

Figure 71: Rotation Model Metric Scale

Trade Matrix

Presented below in Fig. 72 is the trade matrix showcasing the results of the study. Based on the selected metrics and their weights, a custom three axis rotation stand is the best option for the project.

Category	Weight	Air Table	Stop Motion	Goniometer	Custom 3 Axis Rotating Stand
Variability	0.3	1	5	4	5
Controlability	0.15	1	1	4	4
Visibility/Obstruction of Sensor FOV	0.2	5	3	3	3
Cost	0.15	3	4	2	4
Complexity	0.2	5	3	4	3
TOTAL	1	2.9	3.45	3.5	3.9

Figure 72: Trade Matrix of Rotation Model

Motor Selection

After research and analysis of the torque demands needed from the three motors, a combination of the two choices were applied. One stepper motor will be used to drive the L arm serving as motor 3, due to the higher torque demands this component will experience. Two rotation servos will be used for motors 1 2. These will ensure the weight is kept to minimum and meet the torque demands of their required components. As such, no detailed trade study was conducted.

Truth Data

Trade Metrics

There are four metrics that were chosen to evaluate these sensor options: fidelity, feasibility, size/obtrusiveness, and data capture rate. Table Table 15 below discusses each category, its weight, its driving requirements, and provides a rationale for its selection.

Category	Weight	Driving Requirements	Rationale
Fidelity	0.3	DR 1.1, DR 1.5, DR 1.4	The higher the fidelity of truth data, the better the understanding of tumbling client’s attitude, Euler angles, and angular velocity. This is the most important metric because the estimated accuracy of the test bench sensor suite, as well as the confidence level in the suite performance will be dependent on the accuracy of the truth data.
Feasibility	0.25	DR 1.1, DR 5.2	The hardware needs to be easy to find and purchase, simple to replace if it is broken, and able to be integrated into the design of the selected test stand.
Size/Obtrusiveness	0.2	DR 1.3	It is important that the sensors used to collect truth data do not interfere with the rotational test stand or client object. This means that the sensor(s) should be much smaller in dimension and mass than the client object and electronics needed for the sensors should be minimal and unobtrusive to the test stand motion.
Data Capture Rate	0.25	DR 1.1, DR 5.2	The time step between when each truth data measurement taken is important because it is the defining measurement from which to determine the accuracy of the sensor suite. The data capture rate is desired to be as high as possible to that it will match or exceed that of the selected sensor suite.

Table 15: Client Truth Data Trade Metrics Table with Rationale and Driving Requirements

Trade Metric Scale

Figure 73 below outlines the scale used to rank each sensor option for the defined metric trade metric above.

Metric	1	2	3	4	5
Fidelity	Prone to propugating errors	Extensive noise in measurements	extensive post-processing needed to aquire desired data	multiple measurements that can be compared for verification and validity	fine measurements with little noise or uncertainty
Feasibility	Very diffucult to assemble/replace/purchase	Difficult to assemble/replace/purchase	Able to assemble/replace/purchase	Easy to assemble/replace/purchase	Very easy to assemble/replace/purchase
Size\Obrusiveness	Blocks test stand motion and/or throws off target object rotation	Interferes with test stand motion and/or is very pronounced on target object	Manigable size, minimal interference with test stand	Small in size, minimal interference with test stand	Very small, light weight, no interference with test stand
Data Cature Rate	N/A	0-50 kHz	50-90 kHz	N/A	~100 kHz

Figure 73: Trade Matrix Scale of Truth Data

Trade Matrix

In Figure 74 below the trade matrix showcases the results of the truth data sensor trade study. Based on the selected metrics and their defined weight, the rotary encoders are the most desired sensor for collecting truth data.

Category	Weight	Accelerometer	Gyroscope	IMU	Rotary encoder
Fidelity	0.3	2	3	4	5
Feasibility	0.25	5	4	5	5
Size	0.2	4	4	4	5
Data Capture Rate	0.25	5	5	5	3
TOTAL	1	3.9	3.95	4.5	4.5

Figure 74: Trade Matrix of Truth Data

10.1.3.3 Baseline Design

Rotational Dynamics of Physical Model

Modeling the rotation of a tumbling object will be done using a custom 3 axis rotation stand. The other options available in the trades either have a very high cost or are too restricting to the model design. The goniometer is too high of a cost and the client would need to be specifically designed to fit within the configuration of the goniometer. The air table does not allow for enough variability and is severely limited in how many realistic scenarios can be tested. The custom stand will be designed specifically around the model space debris using low cost materials and will be driven by motors. A baseline design of the custom stand that will be constructed is shown below.

Figure 75: Baseline Design of 3 Axis Rotating Stand

Truth Data

The rotary encoders will be used to provide truth data of the client tumbling debris object. This sensor combines the benefits of both the accelerometer and gyroscope, providing accurate measurements of linear and angular accelerations and velocities. Since the encoder can be mounted directly to an axis connected to the tumbling client debris object there is no uncertainty that the measurements made by the sensor are of the client objects motion. Furthermore, since the truth data collected during tumbling tests does not need to be compared the sensor suite during the test, truth data can be stored on an internal SD card and transmitted via Bluetooth for analysis post test. This eliminates the physical electrical wiring needed to integrate this sensors to the test stand, reducing its interference with the motion of the test stand itself.

10.1.4 Servicer System

10.1.4.1 Conceptual Design Alternatives

10.1.4.1.1 Sensor Suite

Stereo Cameras

A stereo camera is a type of camera that uses multiple sensors to create depth perception, similar to how our eyes work. Taking multiple images at different angles generates a high degree of accuracy of the distance between the camera and the object, which is not present in mono-cameras [?]. This can map pixels to the real world through post-image processing. The stereo camera is readily available and has many uses. Many of the applications involve drones, automobiles, surveillance, etc.

Figure 76: Stereo Camera Triangulation

The stereo camera gets the distance by setting up a 2D mapping in one of the camera's orientations. The angle between the two cameras connects the object in a 3D reference frame. This

triangulation is what makes this camera so useful. This can be seen in Figure 76. The stereo camera is relevant to our project as it can visualize and find the distance between the stereo camera and the space debris. Although the stereo camera has these upsides, it is still limited. One of the major downsides is that the stereo camera performance is dependent on sunlight. The camera still needs some visual electromagnetic waves to measure the distance. There are variations of the sensors that make it an active sensor with a projector light as seen in Figure 77. However, this is still limited over long ranges, as it may not pick up the reflecting signals that it emits. The stereo camera is more suited to intermediate and short distances.

Figure 77: Active Stereo Camera

If the spacecraft was near the space debris, a stereo camera can measure many aspects like the distance and shape of the debris. Affordable stereo cameras have good sampling rates and resolutions which is ideal for this project. Combining this sensor with another sensor can solve some of the stereo camera shortcomings.

Pros	Cons
Collects whole image at once	Passive Sensor
Wide FOV	Computation Intensive
Measures Visual information and Distance	Short to Medium Range
	Sensitive to Light

Monocular Cameras

A monocular camera is a type of camera that captures images by using one camera. This camera receives visible electromagnetic waves and captures them. These cameras can capture these images at a high rate and stitches them together. It only has one camera so the advantage seen in the stereo camera is not present in the monocular camera. Monocular cameras can map pixels from the images to the real world through post-processing. Monocular cameras are highly available and have many applications. Monocular cameras have been seen in automated driving, aircraft object detection, etc.

Figure 78: Monocular Camera vs Stereo Camera FOV

Monocular cameras work as a stereo camera but with one camera. This has some advantages. This is simpler to implement on the hardware side. Images can be fed into the processing system directly without triangulation or any other process. It also can detect movement and changes in the object movement as it captures sequences of images of the object. Unlike stereo cameras, objects too close to the sensor can still be seen. This is shown in Figure 78. These advantages are much simpler than the stereo camera but suffer major drawbacks compared to the stereo camera. Monocular cameras can only detect the light of the object and not distance like a stereo camera. It is possible to measure depth with monocular cameras but it requires depth estimation with the use of highly complex software implementation [?]. Just like the stereo camera, the monocular

camera is a passive sensor. Therefore processing the shape of the object still requires sunlight to cover the space debris. The effective range of the monocular is short to intermediate, unlike some LIDAR options.

Pros	Cons
Collects whole image at once	Passive Sensor
Wide FOV	Short and Medium Range
	Visual Data Only
	Sensitive to Light

Scanning LiDAR

Scanning LIDAR is a type of LIDAR that sweeps an area with an electromagnetic wave and receives back that signal. It emits the signals by shooting a laser into a spinning mirror. The mirror reflects the lasers in an area which can then be received by the sensor when it reflects. Scanning LIDAR, like most LIDAR sensors, measures the distance between the sensor and the object. This can map points into a point cloud and give the general image of the space debris. This can also indicate how far away the object is. This type of LIDAR has many applications such as mapping surrounding terrain from an aircraft [?].

Figure 79: 3D Scanning LIDAR Vertical Scanning

Scanning LIDAR measures the distance of an object by emitting lasers into a spinning mirror. Although there are many different types of scanning LIDAR, 3D scanning LIDAR is most applicable to this project. 3D scanning lasers have multiple lasers emitting into a lens. The mirror can spin such that the laser that is emitted scans in a vertical line instead of a point in space. This is shown in Figure 79. This lowers the sampling needed to analyze space debris. Scanning LIDAR is relevant with our project being it is an active sensor. It does not need the sun to measure distance. This allows for visualization without any assistance. Without needing assistance from solar light, it lowers the sampling time to map the space debris. However, because the sensor is based on a spinning mirror and scans horizontally, visualizing the object may be difficult if the object is tumbling fast enough. If the object is tumbling fast enough, the shape of the object will be distorted.

Pros	Cons
High Range	Collects Data Horizontally
Active Sensor	Lower Sampling Rate
High Accuracy	Accuracy Depends on Material

Scannerless Continuous-Wave LIDAR

Continuous-wave LIDAR (CW LIDAR) is a type of LIDAR that emits a continuous array of light that can measure the entire surface of an object at once. This allows continuous wave LIDAR to measure rotating objects accurately. Many of the downsides of using LIDAR is that it was only able to measure velocity through post-processing, which can have a degree of inaccuracy. Continuous-wave LIDAR eliminates the post-processing of velocity. Many applications for this sensor are in the autonomous driving industry [?].

Figure 80: FMCW LIDAR Modulation

Similar to radio systems, there are frequency modulated continuous wave (FMCW) LIDAR as well as amplitude modulated continuous wave (AMCW) LIDAR. FMCW LIDAR measures the velocity of an object by continuously emitting a laser array to an object with a specific frequency. This frequency is modulated so that it can detect the distance between the low and high-frequency points [?]. If the object is moving, the laser frequency creates a doppler wave, which can be measured as a distance by the sensor. This can be seen in Figure 80 These waves are received by the sensor and then demodulated. This system protects itself from the many downsides of LIDAR, mainly protection from solar light and other sources of noise. Because of the modulation and demodulation, the sensor can precisely detect and amplify its signal when received. However, many of the downsides of FMCW LIDAR are how undeveloped the technology is and the lack of lateral velocity measurements. FMCW LIDAR has just been integrated with autonomous driving

vehicles. It has not reached a point, like time of flight LIDAR, of high degrees of accuracy and reliability. This can be detrimental when de-tumbling the space debris. Another downside is it does not measure lateral velocity well. Because FMCW LIDAR mainly measures from the longitude motion, measuring a tumbling object may not be great with this sensor.

Pros	Cons
Measure Velocity	Can not measure lateral velocity
Active Sensor	Emerging Technology
High Accuracy	

Scannerless Pulsed LIDAR

Pulsed LIDAR is a type of LIDAR that emits a pulse of electromagnetic waves in a given area at the same time. This is used to measure the distance between the sensor and the object using time of flight tracking [?]. It solves the downsides of scanning LIDAR by not having to measure the object horizontally but instantly. This is shown in Figure 81. This technology is used in autonomous technology as there is no distortion within the point cloud.

Figure 81: Pulse LIDAR’s FOV

Pulse LIDAR is a scanning LIDAR but with the ability to measure a FOV range instantly like

a camera. This ability carried many advantages from LIDAR and a camera to pulse LIDAR. Many advantages include the sensor being an active sensor and not being reliant on solar light. This lowers the sampling time needed to shape the space debris. Pulse LIDAR also does not need any post-processing to fix distortions for high moving or high tumbling objects. This increases the accuracy of the image by removing software errors, and this causes it to have a higher sampling rate. However, it still suffers downsides. Because pulse LIDAR has a greater FOV than scanning LIDAR, it suffers a short distance to be effective. This might affect how close the sensor needs to be near the space debris. It is also sensitive to other light sources which have similar wavelengths to the pulse LIDAR laser. These disadvantages are mended with other sensors but still need to be considered.

Pros	Cons
Collects whole image at once	High Cost
Active Sensor	Accuracy Depends on Material
High Accuracy	
High Sampling Rate	

Spatial Light Modulating LIDAR

Spatial light modulating LIDAR (SLM LIDAR) is a type of LIDAR that uses a shift in phase, amplitude, and polarization of light to measure distance. One of the special features is that it doesn't scan like a traditional LIDAR sensor. It uses a spatial light modulator and receives the waves through a photodetector. This is shown in Figure 82. Because it does not scan and mainly uses a low-cost photodetector and a spatial light modulator, it does not suffer a low sampling rate like scanning LIDAR [?]. This type of LIDAR has applications in holography, optical communications, and biomedical imaging. The application of this sensor in traditional LIDAR industries like autonomous automobiles is still being researched.

Figure 82: SLM LIDAR

SLM LIDAR has many advantages for being able to detect tumbling space debris. It is an active sensor so it can detect the full scale of the object without the assistance of solar light. This allows the post-processing to be quick, compare to other forms of LIDAR, as there is no wait time between the position of the space debris to the sun. Along with that, the sensor has a high sampling rate as it uses spatial light modulation with photodetectors. This allows for a full-scale resolution of the space debris without scanning. This is similar to the pulse LIDAR but without the pulse of electromagnetic waves. The spatial waves are continuously emitting from the sensor. SLM LIDAR still has major disadvantages. SLM LIDAR is still a developing technology for the application of LIDAR. Many technologies that use spatial light modulation are in other fields which do not relate to CROACS. Other fields like mapping/imaging in geography and autonomous automobiles have not fully developed SLM LIDAR technology. Therefore the accuracy and reliability of SLM LIDAR can be disadvantageous to use for accurate analysis of space debris.

Pros	Cons
No Scanning	Complex Software Design
Active Sensor	Low Heritage
Simple Hardware Design	

10.1.4.1.2 On-board Processor

Microcontroller

Microcontrollers are very cost effective small processors, popular examples being the Arduino Uno and Raspberry Pi Pico. Microcontroller boards like these are commonly used in many applications, including, but not limited to, robotics and electronic projects. While cheap and well fitted to many applications, the options considered within this category are limited in processing power, and restrictive in the languages that they are capable of running.

Pros	Cons
Inexpensive	Weakest overall specifications
	Restrictive

Low-spec Microcomputer

Microcomputers are simply small, typically inexpensive computers. Although they are not modifiable in terms of hardware, they are very flexible in what languages and programs they are capable of running. Within the category of low-spec microcomputers, the processors are relatively weaker, and are accompanied by minimal RAM. On the positive side, these lead to very low costs, making low-spec microcomputers an economical option for many projects.

Pros	Cons
Inexpensive	Weak processors
Capable of running any language	Not customizable

Mid-spec Microcomputer

Mid-spec microcomputers are essentially the same as those above, except they have traded an

increase in price for an increase in performance. These boards include faster processors, improved graphics processing, and large increases in memory, while still remaining affordable.

Pros	Cons
Cost Effective	Not customizable
High memory capacity	

Pre-built and Internal Graphics

When looking at high-spec microcomputers, there are minimal differences when compared to smaller pre-built computer systems, and as such, this category intends to encompass both. When looking at these systems, they bring high speed processors with increased processing capabilities and RAM, but also bring a somewhat significant increase in price. Another benefit to these systems is opportunity to customize some aspects of the hardware to better suit the desired application.

Pros	Cons
Fast processors	Not fully customizable
High memory capacity	

Self-built and Internal Graphics

A self-built system allows the greatest ability to design to fit the specific desired application. This does, however, also come with the greatest cost. In this category, all considered computers do not include a dedicated GPU, instead relying on the graphics processing capabilities of the CPUs. These systems offer much of the same hardware as the pre-built options considered above, with much more design freedom.

Pros	Cons
Fastest processor	High cost
Fastest Memory	

Self-built and External Graphics

These systems are the same as those considered above, with the added benefit of a dedicated

GPU. This comes at a significant cost increase, as well as significant performance gains.

Pros	Cons
Highest Specs	Cost prohibitive
Fully customizable	

10.1.4.2 Trade Studies

Sensor Suite

Trade Metrics

Overall, there are 6 metrics that were chosen to evaluate these technologies, namely, software complexity, hardware complexity, effective range, sensitivity to lighting, data density, and sensitivity to rapid movement. Table 16 below discusses each category, its weight, its driving requirements, and provides a rationale for its selection.

Category	Weight	Driving Requirements	Rationale
Software Complexity	0.3	Project Timeline, FR 1, FR 2, DR 2.2	The complexity of software implementation given the time constraints of the project make this an important category to include. And considering the nature of the mission, software is anticipated to be a significant portion, therefore it is heavily weighted.
Hardware Complexity	0.1	Project Timeline, FR 4, DR 4.1, DR 4.2	Similar to the rationale for software complexity, the implementation at a hardware level is another important category to consider when selecting between different technologies. However, it is not as critical to mission success, and therefore weighted accordingly.
Effective Range	0.1	DR 1.3	Overall, it is important to consider the operating range of each technology, but considering the relatively short range of our mission, it is not weighted very heavily.
Sensitivity to Lighting	0.15	DR 1.5	Considering some of the technologies are passive sensors, the sensitivity to lighting conditions is important for all aspects of client characterization.
Data Density	0.2	FR 2, DR 1.4, DR 2.1	Whether it be from the number of points in a point cloud or the resolution of an image, data density is directly related to the ability to characterize the client in all aspects (position, orientation, and angular velocity). This is why it is the most weighted category behind the overall software complexity.
Sensitivity to Rapid Movement	0.15	FR 2, DR 1.1, DR 5.2	Considering orientation and angular velocity of the client are key objectives of the project, the ability to sense a rapidly moving client is important, more so than both effective range and overall hardware complexity.

Table 16: Trade Metrics Table with Rationale and Driving Requirements

Trade Metric Scale

Figure 83 below outlines the scale used to rank each technology for a given metric for the sensor trade matrix.

Metric	1	2	3	4	5
Software Complexity	Cutting edge technology that is still being researched OR requires advanced algorithms for 2D to 3D conversion.	Research/ Documentation is available, previous missions have implemented the technology.	Research/Documentation is widely available and there are a variety of missions that have implemented the technology.	Research/Documentation is widely available, commercial software is available, and there are a variety of missions that have implemented the technology.	Wide variety of commercial software is available, possible tutorials for implementation.
Hardware Complexity	Hardware requires extensive assembly/modification, has many internal moving parts, and/or isn't commercially available	Sensor has internal moving parts and may require assembly/modification	N/A	Sensor has no moving parts, does not require assembly/modification, but isn't commonly available	Commonly available hardware, reliable, and requires no assembly/modification to implement.
Effective Range	Poor operational range (<20m)	N/A	Operational range is either very close (<5m), very far (>100m), or is directly dependent on specific architecture (width between cameras)	N/A	Extremely wide operational range (0.5m to >1km)
Sensitivity to Lighting	Inherently passive sensor, requires favorable lighting conditions or modifications to make active.	N/A	N/A	Illuminates portions of the scene based on pre-determined pattern, Partially active, partially passive.	Inherently active sensor, doesn't require favorable lighting conditions or modifications.
Data Density	Pixel Size >1mm OR <10,000 points per second in point cloud	N/A	7micrometers < Pixel Size < 1mm, OR 10,000 < point cloud density < 100,000 points per second, OR may commonly exhibit distortion, blurring, or other effects	Pixel size is nominally < 7micrometers OR point cloud density > 100,000 points per second, but may commonly exhibit distortion, blurring, or other effects	Pixel size < 7 micrometers or point cloud density >100,000 points per second
Sensitivity to Rapid Movement	Requires stationary or very slowly rotating targets.	N/A	High speeds are possible, but require expensive and computationally intensive sensors.	N/A	Are generally found with high frame rate or are continuously sensing.

Figure 83: Sensor Metric Scale

Trade Matrix

Presented below in Fig. 84 is the trade matrix showcasing the results of the study. Based on the selected metrics and their weights, a continuous wave LIDAR sensor is the best choice for the project.

Category	Weight	Stereo Cameras	Monocular Camera	Scanning LIDAR	Scannerless LIDAR	Spatial Light Modulating LIDAR
Software Complexity (lower is more complex)	0.3	2	1	3	2	1
Hardware Complexity (lower is more complex)	0.1	5	5	2	4	4
Effective Range	0.1	3	3	5	5	3
Sensitivity to Lighting	0.15	1	1	5	5	4
Data Density	0.2	5	4	3	3	5
Sensitivity to Rapid Movement	0.15	5	5	1	5	3
TOTAL	1	3.3	2.8	3.1	3.6	3.05

Figure 84: Trade Matrix of Sensor Technology

On-board Processor

Trade Metrics

Category	Weight	Driving Requirements	Rationale
Cost	0.3	Budget	Budget is a heavily weighted consideration due to the rapid ramp up in costs with increasing processing power and customizability. The limited budget available is the reason for the weight given.
Compatibility	0.3	FR 2	The chosen processor/computer must be capable of running the chosen algorithm, with powerful enough hardware. This weighting includes the limitations that would be placed on languages that can be run and the level to which we can optimize hardware.
Processor Speed	0.2	FR 3, DR 3.1, DR 3.2	The processor must be capable of receiving and interpreting information at a high enough rate, such that it is capable of running the algorithm at a high enough speed to create useful data.
Graphics Speed	0	FR 3, DR 3.2	Graphics processing is commonly used in many algorithms, but while dedicated graphics processing is beneficial, it is not required, resulting in a lower weight to this category.
Memory	0.2	FR 3, DR 3.1, DR 3.2	Similar to the processor, the chosen RAM must also be capable of receiving and interpreting information at a high enough rate.

Table 17: On-board Processor Trade Metrics Table with Rationale and Driving Requirements

Trade Metric Scale

Metric	1	2	3	4	5
Cost	≥\$650	\$350-649	\$150-349	\$50-149	<\$50
Compatibility	Restricted choice of programming language, processing specifications are fixed	Flexible choice of programming language, processing specifications are fixed	Flexible choice of programming language, processing specifications are somewhat modifiable	Flexible choice of programming language, processing specifications are mostly customizable	Flexible choice of programming language, processing specifications fully customizable
Processor Speed	<1 GHz	1-1.4 GHz	1.5-1.9 GHz	2-2.9 GHz	≥3 GHz
Graphics Speed	No graphics processing included	<0.5 GHz	0.5-0.9 GHz	1-1.4 GHz	≥1.5 GHz
Memory	<1 GB	1-2 GB	2-3.9 GB	7-7.9 GB	≥8GB

Figure 85: On-board Processor Metric Scale

Trade Matrix

After further analysis into how we are optimizing our algorithm and developing new algorithms through the use of parallel processing in Matlab, we found that a far greater importance would be placed on the processor, with none on the graphics, beyond the capability of displaying the user environment. In this updated trade study, we found that a custom built computer would give use the greatest ability to run our algorithm, allowing for choice of individual components that best fit our usage.

Category	Weight	Microcontroller	Low-spec Microcomputer	Mid-spec Microcomputer	Pre-built, internal graphics	Self-built, internal graphics	Self-built, external graphics
Cost	0.3	5	5	4	3	2	1
Compatibility	0.3	1	2	2	3	4	5
Processor Speed	0.2	1	2	3	5	5	5
Graphics Speed	0	1	2	3	4	4	5
Memory	0.2	1	1	5	5	5	5
TOTAL	1	2.2	2.7	3.4	3.8	3.8	3.8

Figure 86: Trade Matrix of On-board Processor

10.1.4.3 Baseline Design

Sensor Suite

Looking back at Fig. 84, a scannerless LIDAR sensor was selected for the baseline design. This is based on the research done on these sensors in general, their capabilities, and their advantage in terms of sensitivity to rapid movement when compared to scanning LIDAR. Stereo cameras were the next closest option, but were ruled out because of their inadequate performance under poor lighting conditions.

On-board Processor

The pre-built, internal graphics computer was chosen for our onboard processing requirements. This option provides the greatest balance of cost and performance, and although it does not offer as

many options to customize as a self-built system, it fully supports the programs necessary. These reasons, weighted above in section 5, led to the conclusion that this system is the best choice available for our goals.

10.2 Appendix B: Verification and Validation

10.2.1 LiDAR Data Quality

Figure 87: Captured Point Cloud of Client, Side POV

Figure 87 corresponds to Figure 30, but rotated 90 degrees to the side. As seen in this figure, there are significant distortions in the scanning direction. When we first researched time-of-flight LiDAR sensors, the data that we saw showed no signs of this distortion. The software tried several mitigation techniques to reduce this distortion, but nothing that we implemented showed any real effect. We believe that this distortion played a large role in the error that we saw in our testing

results. A zoomed in point cloud of our client with this y-spread distortion can be seen in Figure 88.

Figure 88: Point Cloud of Client with Distortion

10.2.2 Software Identification Test Attitude Results

The results for the attitude portion of the Software Identification Test can be found in Figures 89 through 91. Similar to our Day in the Life results, our x-axis solution is not very accurate compared to the truth. This stems from the y-spread of the point clouds as well as the symmetry of the client along that axis. Unfortunately, the only solutions to this problem are to implement a different LiDAR or use a different tumbling body, both of which were not possible given the time frame of the project and how much effort we had already put in. The y-axis results are the best of the three, thanks in part to the variation in the points when matching to the y-axis. The z-axis is inbetween the x- and y- in regards to accuracy to the truth. The estimate is off by approximately 15 degrees, which does fall under our required error limits. However, similar to the x-axis, we believe

that this estimation was impacted by the quality of the LiDAR

Figure 89: X-Axis Stationary Results

Figure 90: Y-Axis Stationary Results

Figure 91: Z-Axis Stationary Results